

**RAJA NARENDRALAL KHAN WOMEN'S COLLEGE
(AUTONOMOUS)**

NATIONAL CONFERENCE

on

**Climate Change, Biodiversity and
Environmental Sustainability**

Sponsored by

**Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology
(DSTBT), Government of West Bengal**

12-13 March, 2026

Book of Abstract

Organised

By

**Research Centre in Natural and Applied Sciences
Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous)
Midnapore-721102, West Bengal**

Professor Dipak Kumar Kar

Vice-Chancellor
Vidyasagar University
Midnapore - 721102
West Bengal, India

Website : www.vidyasagar.ac.in

E-mail:

vc@mail.vidyasagar.ac.in

vcconfidential@mail.vidyasagar.ac.in

drdipakkumarkar@gmail.com

Mobile:

7044577044

8597748052

9064236649

VIDYASAGAR UNIVERSITY

Date: 02.03.2026

MESSAGE

It gives me immense pleasure to extend my warm greetings and best wishes on the occasion of the Two-day National Conference on *Climate Change, Biodiversity and Environmental Sustainability*, on March 12 & 13, 2026, organised by the Natural and Applied Sciences Research Centre of Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore and sponsored by the Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology, Government of West Bengal.

In an era marked by unprecedented environmental challenges, deliberations on climate change, biodiversity conservation and sustainable development have become not only relevant but imperative. The accelerating impacts of global warming, habitat degradation and loss of biodiversity call for informed research, collaborative action and innovative solutions rooted in scientific inquiry and social responsibility.

I am confident that this conference will serve as an important platform for academicians, scientists, policymakers and research scholars to exchange ideas, present cutting-edge research and foster interdisciplinary collaborations. Such academic engagements significantly contribute to developing strategies that balance ecological integrity with developmental aspirations.

I congratulate the Natural and Applied Sciences Research Centre and the entire organising team of Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous) for taking this commendable initiative. I also acknowledge with appreciation the generous support of the Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology, Government of West Bengal, in promoting research and scientific dialogue on issues of national and global importance.

I sincerely hope that the deliberations and outcomes of this conference will inspire actionable insights and meaningful contributions towards achieving environmental sustainability for present and future generations.

I wish the conference every success.

(Professor Dipak Kumar Kar)

Dr. Angsuman Chanda,
Convener, National Conference on *Climate Change, Biodiversity and Environmental Sustainability*,
Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous),
Paschim Medinipur – 721 102

ভারতীয় প্রযুক্তিবিদ্যা প্রতিষ্ঠান খড়্গপুর
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প্রো. রিন্টু বনর্জী, উপ নিদেশক

Prof. Rintu Banerjee, FNASc, FNAAS, FNAScT, FBRS, FAMI

Deputy Director

Professor, Agricultural & Food Engineering Department

Message

I am pleased to learn that the Natural and Applied Sciences Research Centre of Raja N. L. Khan Women's College is organizing a two-day National Conference on “*Climate Change, Biodiversity and Environmental Sustainability*”. Bringing together researchers, teachers, and students to exchange ideas on such an important and timely theme is both valuable and commendable.

At present, the world is facing several critical challenges such as increasing pollution, rising greenhouse gas emissions, global warming driven by anthropogenic activities, and various socio-environmental conflicts. These issues have intensified the impacts of climate change and highlighted its close connection with biodiversity loss, ultimately affecting the stability and functioning of ecosystems. Identifying sustainable solutions to address these interconnected challenges has become an urgent priority.

I hope that the deliberations during this conference will contribute to a better understanding of the interconnections between climate change, biodiversity, and environmental sustainability. The exchange of ideas and research outcomes will undoubtedly contribute to ongoing scientific efforts in this field.

I congratulate the organizers for their initiative in hosting this conference and wish the event every success.

(Rintu Banerjee) 5/3/2026

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Message from Principal

Date: 09.03.2026

It gives me immense pleasure to extend a warm welcome to all scholars, researchers, students, and distinguished participants to the two-day National Conference on “**Climate Change, Biodiversity and Environmental Sustainability,**” organized by the Research Centre in Natural and Applied Sciences of Raja Narendralal Khan Women’s College. Bringing together researchers, teachers, and students to exchange ideas on such an important and timely theme is both valuable and commendable. This conference reflects our institution’s continued commitment to academic excellence and societal relevance. Climate change and biodiversity loss are among the most pressing environmental challenges of our time. Rapid environmental transformations are affecting ecosystems, natural resources, and human livelihoods across the globe. In this context, it is essential to promote scientific research, interdisciplinary dialogue, and collective action aimed at environmental sustainability and responsible resource management.

I am confident that this conference will provide a vibrant platform for interdisciplinary dialogue, knowledge exchange, and critical reflection on the scientific, social, and policy dimensions of climate change and biodiversity conservation. I sincerely acknowledge the kind support of the *Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT), Government of West Bengal*, whose funding has made this academic endeavour possible. I congratulate the organizing committee for their initiative and wish the conference every success. I hope it will inspire meaningful research, collaboration, and action towards environmental conservation and sustainable development.

With best wishes,

Dr. Swapna Ghorai

DR. SWAPNA GHORAI
Principal

Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College
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Midnapore, West Bengal

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ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

Climate change and environmental degradation have become major global challenges affecting ecosystems, biodiversity, and human livelihoods. Rising levels of air, water, and land pollution, along with deforestation, biodiversity loss, and increasing greenhouse gas emissions, threaten environmental sustainability worldwide. Addressing these issues requires coordinated global efforts, the adoption of clean technologies, and sustainable management of natural resources. Renewable energy sources such as solar and wind power, reduced dependence on fossil fuels, and the conservation of forests and biodiversity are increasingly emphasized in global environmental policies. In the Indian context, environmental sustainability is not only a contemporary concern but also deeply rooted in traditional knowledge systems. Ancient Indian texts such as the Vedas, Smṛtis, Purāṇas, Arthaśāstra, and the Epics reflect a strong ecological consciousness and promote a harmonious relationship between humans and nature. These texts highlight moral responsibilities for protecting the environment and emphasize the consequences of actions affecting nature.

The two-day National Conference on “*Climate Change, Biodiversity and Environmental Sustainability (CBES-26)*”, organized by the Research Centre in Natural and Applied Sciences, Raja Narendralal Khan Women’s College, aims to bring together scholars, researchers, teachers, and students to share ideas and research on this important and timely theme. The conference reflects the institution’s commitment to academic excellence and environmental awareness.

Dr. Angsuman Chanda, *Joint Convener*

Dr. Sukumar Mondal, *Joint Convener*

Dr. Pravat Kumar Shit, *Joint Organizing Secretary*

Dr. Sujoy Midya, *Joint Organizing Secretary*

Raja Narendralal Khan Women’s College (Autonomous), Midnapore-721102

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Understanding interlinkages among biodiversity, climate change and sustainability acts as prerequisite for undertaking proper environmental planning and management

Susanta Kumar Chakraborty
Former, Vice Chancellor, Vidyasagar University
Midnapore -721102, West Bengal, India
Email: susantachakrabortyzoology@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Biodiversity being “the variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems which includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems” and is considered as biological wealth of the Earth by virtue of their potential for providing necessary ingredients for the survivability of human beings. Climate change refers to long-term shifts in global temperatures and weather patterns, primarily driven by human activities since the initiation phase of Industrial Revolution in Europe, mainly because of overuse and burning fossil fuels. Greenhouse gases released by human activities act like a blanket trapping heat and thereby raising Earth’s average temperature. Sustainable development is an approach to growth and human development that aims to meet the needs of the moment without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs by rationale and judicious use of natural resources. Achieving sustainable development requires eradication of poverty and hunger, ensure supply of safe water to every citizen, reduce inequality and all of these contribute in a synergistic manner for maintaining sound ecological health of ecosystems which is happened to be because of the interlinkages among climate, biodiversity, and sustainable development in different sectors of the society.

Alongside large scale usage of fossil fuels, massive alteration of land use patterns resulting the expansion of agriculture, deforestation, over harvesting of bio-resources, generation of different kinds of pollution in conjunction with climate change mediated global warming cause biodiversity loss and contribute to all round eco-degradation climate change. Climate change is characterized with enhanced temperatures, changing patterns of rain fall, wind flow etc. leading to cause extreme and unpredictable weather events. The impacts of climate change on biodiversity are compounded by other forms of pollution like acidification due to increased atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations, shifting geographic ranges of species, migration patterns and modes of species interactions within biotic community seasonal abundance of flora and fauna, bioinvasion, eutrophication, destruction of ozone layer, El-Nino etc. Around one million of animal and plant species are appeared to have been threatened to experience extinction as a result of human activities, mainly in the urbanized and industrialized societies. Local species richness, the number of different species in an ecosystem, is estimated to have fallen by around 14% on average due to human activity and more than 75% in the worst affected habitats. A recent estimate has shown that 4% of vertebrates, 8% of plants and 6% of

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insects have been projected to lose over half of their climate-determined geographic range due to an increase of 1.5°C of warming, whereas at under 3°C rises in temperature dramatically cause the decline of 26% of vertebrates, 44% of plants, and 49% of all insects.

Climate change mediated disruption of ecosystems functioning makes ecosystems more vulnerable as well as resilient to varying and shifting climates and biodiversity secures these climate regulating functions as biodiversity components (flora, fauna, water and sediments) most of which act as reservoirs of carbon. Any alteration in these carbon reservoirs caused by direct human activity, climate change, or other modes of pollution significantly affect the climate in general and ecosystem functioning (the flows of energy and cyclical movement of matter) in particular. The feedback loops between climate change and biodiversity loss tend to regulate trend of present modes of development for meeting the basic needs of the society as this feedback loop with the loss of biodiversity causes reduction of the planet's ability to sequester carbon, worsening negative consequences due to climate change whereas ecologically stable ecosystems provide crucial climate mitigation.

The success of addressing and achieving the desired goals tackling the global issues like climate change, biodiversity loss, eutrophication, acidification and sustainable development rest upon reduction of emissions from fossil fuels and undertaking judicious action plans for natural resource management through proper land uses which in turn reversing the destruction and degradation of ecosystems.

The prime challenge of the present time is to tackle environmental problems associated with climate change and loss of biodiversity. Innumerable biological organisms through their continuous interactions sustain human life by rendering ecosystem services as supplier of food, clean water, fresh water, control of pests and pathogens. However, eco-assessment of the impact of climate change on biodiversity is difficult, because the effects of climate change on biodiversity can be grouped into: (i) spatial and temporal distributions of taxa; (ii) migration and dispersal potentials of taxa; (iii) existing genetic diversity and viability of development meta-populations of species; (iv) acquiring physiological tolerance of species; (v) disruption of functional interactions among species and (vi) ground truth information of normal ecosystem processes.

Nature-based Solutions (NbS) can contribute to mitigation and adaptation, in the face of adverse impacts of climate change and ensure conservation of ecosystems like wetlands, reducing deforestation and promoting ecosystem restoration, through increasing carbon sequestration and ecosystem resilience to climate change which meet the requirements for achieving some mandates of sustainable development goals (SDGs). In addition, ecosystem-based approaches to adaptation and disaster risk reduction can also reduce the negative impacts of climate change in the process of providing benefits for water filtration, flood regulation, maintenance of soil health and habitats for biodiversity components and enhancement of climate resilience.

In view of these propositions, an interdisciplinary research programme is required to be developed which could possibly generate input data to be used for developing predictive models based on climate change scenarios. Governments should focus international attention on the interconnectedness

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and interdependence of climate change and biodiversity with an aim at achieving proper mitigation strategies, adaptation to climate change and conservation of biodiversity, all of which combinedly help achieve major targets of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). These interconnections and outlines of generated research outcomes render benefits to biodiversity which have the potential to support climate action. Some emerging major recommendations associated with interconnections among biodiversity, climate change and biodiversity are: 1) The global environmental issues such as climate change mediated harmful impacts on ecosystem functioning along with biodiversity loss tend to impose their negative impacts undermining many Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), challenging the stability both in environmental and social sectors; 2) The increasing crises pertaining to climate and biodiversity should not only be considered as mutually fortifying acute emergent ecological problems but delaying action instead of taking immediate action to tackle the situation tends to result costlier damages to society and economy; 3) Transformative changes are required to decarbonise the economy and reverse the destruction and degradation of ecosystems; 4) Climate, biodiversity, and society are inter linked, requiring synergies and coherence in policies and actions, in particular, related to nationally determined contributions (NDCs), National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), and National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs); 5) Nature-based solutions (NbS) include biodiversity conservation and eco-restoration measures that support climate change mitigation, adaptation, and sustainable development. However, climate change also affects ecosystems and reduces their potential to serve as NbS; 6) Proper understanding of underlying ecological principles can provide knowledge, tools, and methods for assessing the interlinkages of climate, biodiversity, and sustainable development and contribute to participatory decision-making processes for navigating synergies, trade-offs, and uncertainties; 7) environmental-policy processes that bring together actors with different knowledge on climate, biodiversity, and sustainable development can support the co-creation and implementation of more coherent policies and actions from the local to the global scale. In view of all such understandings, one has to have basic knowledge on relevancies on different terminologies like climate crisis, global warming, green house effects, Green House Gases (Chlorofluorocarbons, Carbon di Oxide (CO₂), Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x), Nitrous Oxide(N₂O), water vapour), carbon-budget, Carbon Footprint, climate resilience, carbon sequestration, zero-emission, climate adaptation and adaptive capacity, Feedback Mechanisms, Intergovernmental Panel on climate Change (IPCC), United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, (UNFCCC), vulnerability, zero-emission etc. in such context, it is now imperative to device and apply eco-friendly and user friendly innovative technologies to slow down the present accelerated pace of ongoing climate change mediated global warming emphasizing more onto stewardship and participation of people.

Keywords: *Climate Change; Biodiversity Conservation; Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); Global Warming; Greenhouse Gas Emissions; Nature-Based Solutions (NbS); Innovative Environmental Management Technologies; People's Stewardship; Community Participation; Sustainable Resource Management.*

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**Climate Change: Causes, Consequences, Mitigation, and Solutions for a Sustainable
Future**

Sanjat Kumar Sahu

Adjunct Professor of Environmental Science, Berhampur University,

Bhanja Bihar-760007, Ganjam, Odisha, India

Email: sahusanjat@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

One of the most urgent global issues of our time is climate change, which has an impact on every part of the world and our lives. Climate Change refers to significant alterations in global temperatures and weather patterns over time. While climate variability is natural to some extent, but the current phase of rapid change is predominantly due to human activities. The Earth's climate is warming, primarily due to the increased greenhouse gases, burning of fossil fuels, deforestation, and industrial activities. The environment, weather patterns, and human societies are all significantly impacted by climate change. Communities and ecosystems are disrupted as a result of more frequent and severe weather events including heatwaves, droughts, and hurricanes. Coastal regions are at risk from increased erosion and floods due to rising sea levels, which are a result of glaciers and ice caps melting. The natural world faces loss of biodiversity as habitats alters or disappear. Moreover, agricultural productivity is impacted by changing precipitation patterns, affecting food security. Human health risks also rise with the spread of diseases and heat-related illnesses. Therefore, from altering weather patterns to impacting wildlife and human societies, its effects are profound and far-reaching. These impacts underscore the urgency of addressing climate change on a local and global scale.

Combating climate change requires a multifaceted approach involving individual actions, policy changes, and technological innovations. People can help by lowering their carbon footprint, implementing energy-saving techniques, and purchasing sustainable goods. International commitments to prevent global warming by lowering greenhouse gas emissions, such as the Paris Agreement, must be strictly adhered to at the policy level. An environmentally friendly substitute for fossil fuels is highly needed, such as renewable energy sources like solar and wind. Carbon sequestration can be improved by reforestation and sustainable land use. Technological developments in carbon capture, storage, and mitigation are also very important. Together, these initiatives can slow down climate change and open the door to a sustainable future. In this paper all the aspects will be critically discussed.

Keywords: *Climate Change (CC); Causes of CC; Issues of CC; Mitigation Measures; Sustainable Practices.*

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Climate Change and Sustainable Agricultural Intensification: Emerging Issues and Pathways in the Indian Context

Pulak Mishra*
Department of Humanities and Social Sciences
Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur
Kharagpur – 721302 West Bengal
**Email: pmishra@hss.iitkgp.ac.in*

ABSTRACT

While the consequences and implications climate change have been well-recognised in the academic and policy discourses, the underlying dynamics and emerging issues for the agriculture sector require special attention. This is very important, particularly in the context of the South Asian countries that not only house a considerably large proportion of land-constrained farmers, but also face serious challenges with respect to income, food security and nutrition of the vast majority of their population, and hence achieving the sustainable development goals (SDGs) of the United Nations. With climate change leading to ecological losses, resource constraints, and increasing production related risks in the agriculture sector, it is, therefore, imperative to have deeper understanding of the underlying issues and design intervention pathways that can potentially address the emerging challenges with respect to income, food security and nutrition of people living in the region. Given this backdrop and based on the available secondary data and insights from the related studies, the present talk discusses the potential trade-offs between inclusivity and sustainability in the Indian agriculture sector in the context of climate change. The talk also proposes the pathways that can potentially address the emerging challenges. It is suggested that, mitigating the impact of climate change on the agriculture sector requires development of an integrated farming system with emphasis on technology development, institutional reforms, collectivization, and strengthening the value and supply chains.

Keywords: *Climate Change; Sustainability; Inclusivity; Agricultural Intensification; Policies; Institutions; India*

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Strengthening Local Resilience through Spatial Early Warning Systems in Disaster Preparedness and Management

Vishwa Raj Sharma*
Department of Geography
Shaheed Bhagat Singh College, University of Delhi, New Delhi- 110017, India
**Email:vishwaraj.sharma@sbs.du.ac.in*

ABSTRACT

Natural Disasters disproportionately impact vulnerable communities, underscoring the need for localized community early warning systems. Spatial early warning systems (SEWS) leverage geo-spatial tools like GIS, remote sensing, and GPS technologies to enhance community preparedness. SEWS enable authorities to model hazards, identify at-risk populations, and disseminate actionable information. When integrated with community networks, these systems facilitate timely evacuations, asset protection, and rapid response. Case studies from India's flood-pruned rivers and cyclone-exposed coasts highlight how spatial data transforms warnings into anticipatory action. With the help of geo-spatial technologies impact of disasters can be reduced and better planning can be done at the ground level.

Key challenges include bridging tech-skill gaps, ensuring last-mile connectivity, and fostering institutional collaboration. The research paper argues for embedding spatial early warning systems (SEWS) within local governance frameworks to sustain community resilience. Recommendations include investing in localized risk models, hybrid (tech and traditional) warning mechanisms, and inclusive capacity-building programs. By making early warnings spatially explicit and community-centric, SEWS offer a scalable pathway to disaster resilience. This research paper examines how SEWS strengthen local resilience in disaster-prone areas by improving risk mapping, real-time monitoring, and targeted alerts.

Keywords: Vulnerable Communities; Disasters; Disproportionately Affected Populations; Geospatial Technologies; Resilience.

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**Strengthening Climate Adaptation through Natural Resource Inventory in the
Traditional Farming Areas of the Eastern Ghats Highlands**

Partha Pratim Adhikary

ICAR – National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India
Email: ppadhikary@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The Eastern Ghats highlands of India represent a fragile agro-ecological region where agriculture and rural livelihoods are increasingly threatened by climate change. Rising temperatures, erratic rainfall, soil degradation, declining water resources, and biodiversity loss are significantly affecting farm productivity and sustainability in the region. Over the past five decades, the region has experienced an average temperature increase of about 1.2 °C, declining and irregular rainfall patterns, and increasing frequency of extreme weather events, resulting in crop yield reductions, soil erosion, and water scarcity. Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) offers an integrated pathway to address these challenges by simultaneously enhancing agricultural productivity, strengthening climate resilience, and contributing to climate change mitigation. This work reviews the major climate challenges in the Eastern Ghats and highlights a range of CSA practices suitable for the region. Key practices discussed include conservation agriculture, mulching, zero tillage, crop diversification, agroforestry systems, efficient water management techniques such as rainwater harvesting and drip irrigation, climate-resilient crop varieties, and integrated pest and nutrient management. In addition, community-based approaches such as farmer field schools, participatory decision-making, and the integration of indigenous knowledge are emphasized as essential for successful CSA implementation. These practices have demonstrated multiple benefits, including improved soil health, enhanced water-use efficiency, reduced soil erosion, increased crop productivity, carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and improved farmer livelihoods. Despite its potential, the adoption of CSA in the Eastern Ghats faces several challenges, including limited farmer awareness, financial constraints, fragmented landholdings, and weak institutional support. The work therefore outlines strategic recommendations such as policy incentives, strengthened research and development, effective technology dissemination, and collaborative stakeholder networks to accelerate CSA adoption. Overall, the integration of climate-smart practices with local knowledge systems and strong institutional support can significantly enhance the resilience and sustainability of farming systems in the Eastern Ghats highlands while improving the socio-economic well-being of smallholder and tribal communities.

Keywords: *Climate Resilience; Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA); Eastern Ghats Highlands; Sustainable Farming; Soil and Water Conservation*

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Climate Crisis: An Enigma

Jatisankar Bandyopadhyay
*Centre for Environmental Studies
Coastal Observatory and Outreach Centre (COOC) &
Department of Remote Sensing and GIS, Vidyasagar University,
Midnapore -721102, West Bengal.
Email: jatib@mail.vidyasagar.ac.in*

ABSTRACT

Climate change is accelerating changes in the biosphere, human environments, and ocean systems, which is a threat to ecological health and long-term sustainability. To evaluate ecosystem degradation, urban vulnerability, and marine ecosystem stress, the integrated geospatial methods are employed for assessing the spatial-temporal impacts of climate variability. Land surface temperature (LST), vegetation health index (VHI), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), and land use land cover (LULC) were some of the parameters derived through the multi-temporal satellite remote sensing data from ISRO (INSAT, RESOURCESAT), NASA (MODIS and Landsat), and the European Space Agency's Sentinel missions. There is a loss of vegetation and fragmentation of habitat in sensitive areas concerning climate as found in the case study, as indicators of stress in the biosphere and reduced likelihood of carbon sequestration. Flooding risks, in particular, are more prevalent in urban areas, with heightened heat island intensity also being observed in low-lying coastal areas. Sea level rise estimates and Digital Elevation Models (DEM) continue to point to increasing hazards of heavily populated coastal communities. The oceanic data on sea surface temperature (SST) and chlorophyll show an upward trend with falling marine productivity accompanying this coral bleaching regime in reef systems like the Great Barrier Reef. The spatial overlay and hotspot analysis show some significant associations between the climate stressor combinations and spots with highly sensitive ecologies and socio-economic parameters. In combination of GIS (Geographic Information Systems), remote sensing and climate modelling can be used to best assess sustainability as well as for adaptive planning. The evidence underscores the importance of geospatial approaches for tracking climate-related shocks and variability, identifying hot spots, and supporting empirical resilience and mitigation plans. To enhance adaptive ability and protect terrestrial and marine ecosystems under the changing climatic circumstances, sustainable management of natural resources and human settlements requires continuous geospatial monitoring.

Keywords: *Climate Change; Land Surface Temperature (LST); Marine Ecosystem Stress; Biosphere Degradation; Geospatial Analysis; Sustainability Assessment.*

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Application of Geo-AI on Future Urban Growth and Sustainable Cities

Suraj Kumar Mallick
*Department of Geography, Shaheed Bhagat Singh College, University of Delhi,
New Delhi – 110017
Email: surajkumarmallick@sbs.du.ac.in*

ABSTRACT

Rapid urban growth in developing countries increasingly challenges existing urban planning systems and future urban regeneration efforts. Identifying suitable areas for built-up development is therefore essential for achieving sustainable urban planning, particularly in industrial cities. This study evaluates area-specific built-up suitability in the Asansol Municipal Corporation (AMC), India, using GeoAI-based soft-computing techniques, including Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Random Forest (RF), and Support Vector Machines (SVM).

The results indicate that the urban fringes and peripheral zones of Asansol, Kulti, and Raniganj exhibit very high (21.52%, 19.87%, and 26.32%) to high suitability (11.48%, 19.00%, and 27.26%) for future built-up development, primarily due to the availability of vacant land and proximity to essential urban services. In contrast, the southern sector of AMC—particularly along the Damodar River and near mining-affected areas—shows low to very low suitability, driven by inadequate infrastructure and elevated environmental pollution.

Based on these findings, a three-tier urban regeneration framework is proposed to guide sustainable built-up development in AMC, contributing to the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3, 8, 11, 12, and 13. The outcomes of this study provide practical insights for policymakers and planners to identify priority zones for future urban development and regeneration initiatives.

Keywords: *Urban Growth; Built-up Suitability; GeoAI; Urban Regeneration; Sustainable Development Goals*

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Assessment of Agricultural Land Suitability Using Integrated AHP–TOPSIS and Machine Learning Techniques: A Case Study of Pusad Taluka, Yavatmal District, India

Pallavi Bange, Akash Jadhav, Yukta Salvi, Sandipan Das*
*Symbiosis Institute of Geoinformatics,
Symbiosis International (Deemed University), Pune – 411016, India
Email: sandipanraj2002@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Agricultural land suitability assessment is vital for sustainable land use planning, particularly in regions facing growing demands for food production and natural resource optimization. This study introduces an approach which combines the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), and machine learning (ML) techniques to assess agricultural land suitability in Pusad Taluka, Yavatmal District, Maharashtra. Geospatial datasets including slope, soil texture, soil pH, organic carbon, cation exchange capacity (CEC), land use/land cover (LULC), temperature, and rainfall were used to generate thematic layers. AHP was applied to derive the relative importance of each criterion through expert-based pairwise comparisons, while TOPSIS was used to rank land parcels based on their proximity to an ideal solution, generating a suitability classification map. To further enhance the reliability of the classification, machine learning classifiers—K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), and Random Forest (RF)—were implemented. The dataset underwent preprocessing to remove null values and convert categorical suitability classes into numerical values. An 80:20 train–test split was used for model training and evaluation. Model performance was assessed using accuracy, recall, F1-score, confusion matrices, and ROC curves. The classification accuracies achieved were 89% for KNN, 91.9% for DT, and 93% for RF, with Random Forest outperforming the others. Visualization of model results using confusion matrix heatmaps and bar charts provided comparative insights. The integrated AHP–TOPSIS–ML framework effectively captured spatial heterogeneity and expert insights while leveraging data-driven classification, offering a robust methodology for informed land resource planning. Results indicated that 27.4% of the land (103,837.84 ha) is highly suitable, 62.5% moderately suitable, and 2.3% less suitable. This approach supports climate-resilient and sustainable agricultural development in semi-arid agro-ecological zones.

Keywords: *Agricultural Land Suitability; AHP; TOPSIS; GIS; Remote Sensing; Machine Learning.*

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Navigating the Transition toward Sustainable Green Blockchain Ecosystems

Anupam Pattanayak*
Department of Computer Science
Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore-721102, West Bengal, India
**Email: anupam_bca@rn1kwc.ac.in*

ABSTRACT

Blockchain network is an emerging area of digital economy and services. It provides the backbone infrastructure for cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin and Ethereum. It also provides the immutable database that forms the basis for many applications which need to preserve the tamper-proof full transaction records. The distributed ledger adds a new block with sufficient transactions which are confirmed by the majority of the blockchain miners. The mining process is computation intensive. Analysts warn that Bitcoin alone consumes as much energy as a small country. This severely creates obstacles to the 1.5°C target of the Paris Agreement that aims to limit the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C, while targeting to limit it to 1.5°C. The most widely used consensus mechanism is Proof-of-Work (PoW). However, PoW is responsible for much higher energy consumption that results in increased carbon emissions. To mitigate this energy-intensive PoW, one alternative consensus mechanism is to use the efficient Proof-of-Stake (PoS) protocol. PoS reduce energy consumption by over 99% compared to PoW. This PoS is the foundation for green cryptocurrencies and green blockchain, which aim to reduce carbon footprints drastically. These initiatives are promising to reconcile decentralized finance and other decentralized, transparent, immutable applications with a focus on planetary sustainability.

Keywords: *Blockchain; Bitcoin; Cryptocurrency; Proof-of-Work; Proof-of-Stake; Carbon Footprint; Green Blockchain; Green Cryptocurrency.*

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**Forest Fires as an Environmental Crime: Preventing Intentional Burning for
Sustainable Ecosystem Management**

Partha Pratim Jana*

Department of Geography

Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), India

Email: ppjana_geo@rnlkwc.ac.in

ABSTRACT

Forest fires have emerged as a critical global environmental challenge, driven not only by natural factors but increasingly by deliberate human actions. Intentional forest fires—often ignited for land encroachment, illegal logging, expansion of grazing land, shifting cultivation, or short-term economic gains—represent a serious form of environmental crime. Such deliberate burning causes extensive and often irreversible damage to forest ecosystems, resulting in biodiversity loss, degradation of soil fertility, disruption of hydrological cycles, atmospheric pollution, and heightened vulnerability to climate change. Moreover, intentional fires severely affect the livelihoods, health, and cultural practices of forest-dependent communities, thereby raising concerns of environmental injustice. Despite advancements in fire detection technologies, satellite monitoring, and disaster response systems, the incidence of intentional forest fires continues to rise in many regions. This persistence reflects gaps in environmental governance, weak law enforcement, limited institutional coordination, and inadequate public awareness regarding ecological ethics and legal accountability. The problem is further compounded by socio-economic pressures and conflicting land-use priorities. This paper conceptualizes intentional forest fires as an environmental crime and underscores the urgent need for preventive strategies grounded in sustainable ecosystem management. It examines the underlying drivers of deliberate forest burning, assesses its ecological and socio-economic consequences, and critically reviews existing legal and institutional mechanisms aimed at prevention and control. The study advocates a multi-dimensional preventive framework that integrates stringent legal enforcement, community participation, ethical environmental responsibility, and the convergence of scientific approaches with indigenous and traditional ecological knowledge. The paper argues that effective prevention of intentional forest fires is essential not only for forest conservation but also for achieving long-term ecological sustainability, climate resilience, and environmental justice.

Keywords: *Environmental Crime; Intentional Forest Fires; Ecosystem Degradation; Sustainable Ecosystem Management; Environmental Governance.*

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**Induced Breeding and Post-Zygotic Development of Rosy Barb, *Pethia conchonius*
(Hamilton, 1822) Under Captive Condition.**

Angsuman Chanda* and Purnachandra Das
Research Centre in Natural and Applied Sciences
Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), affiliated to Vidyasagar University,
Midnapur, Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal-721102, India.
**Email: chandaangsuman182@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Live specimens of *Pethia conchonius* (Hamilton, 1822) were collected from the Kangsabati River and transported to the aquarium facility of the Postgraduate Department of Zoology, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), where they were acclimatized under controlled laboratory conditions. The broodstock successfully thrived in glass tanks for 1.5 months, receiving a balanced diet with Tubifex worms and balanced commercial feed. Sex differentiation of brooders was based on external morphology, with females exhibiting a distended abdomen and males showing a comparatively firm and slender body shape. Induced breeding was carried out using Ovatide at a dose of 2 ml kg⁻¹ body weight for both sexes. Two sex ratios (male: female = 2:1 and 1:1) were tested in separate trials. Spawning occurred within 8–9 hours following hormone administration. The mean fertilization and hatching rates were 90.5% and 85.39%, respectively. Embryonic development proceeded rapidly, with hatching occurring within 7–9 hours at a water temperature of 31–33°C. The diameter of fertilized eggs averaged 0.10 mm. Sequential developmental stages from zygote to embryo, followed by larval development and rearing of juveniles up to 15 days, were systematically documented to provide baseline data relevant for hatchery management. The present study provides comprehensive information on captive breeding, embryogenesis, and early life history of *Pethia conchonius*, addressing existing knowledge gaps and offering practical insights for aquaculture production and conservation of this commercially valuable freshwater ornamental species in Indian riverine systems.

Keywords: *Pethia conchonius*; Induced Breeding; Ovatide; Embryonic Development; Aquaculture; Conservation.

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**Effect of *Moringa oleifera* Leaf Meal as a Fishmeal Substitute on Growth Performance
and Haematological Parameters of *Labeo bata***

Alisha Khatun* and Kartik Maiti

*Research centre in Natural & Applied Sciences
Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Mednapore- 721102, West Bengal, India.
* Email: alishakhatun2000@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

The growing expansion of aquaculture has produced a pressing need for economical, nutritionally balanced feeds, especially for *Labeo bata*, one of the most widely cultivated fish species globally. Fishmeal, the traditional protein source, is costly and unsustainable. *Moringa oleifera*, often called the miracle tree, presents a promising alternative thanks to its high levels of protein, vitamins, and minerals. The present study evaluated the growth performance and haematological parameters of *Labeo bata* over 90 days by substituting varying ratios of *M. oleifera* leaves for fish meal (FM). Five distinct dietary groups were established using a basal diet supplemented with varied proportions of *M. oleifera* leaf meal, substituting T1 (0% MOL), T2 (25% MOL), T3 (50% MOL), T4 (75% MOL), and T5 (100% MOL) for the FM component of the diets. The findings revealed significant differences in growth parameters, with the fish fed the T4 (75% MOL) diet showing, in comparison to the other diets, the highest final weight and specific growth rate. Fish fed D4 diets had significantly increased mean values for both red blood cells and white blood cells. In conclusion, the aqua-feed industry may use MOL in place of 75% FM to improve *Labeo bata* growth and health. It can also improve fish's ability to withstand adverse environmental conditions and improve their haematological function.

Keywords: *Fish meal; Moringa leaf; Growth performance; Health status*

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**Relationship between livelihood of fisherman community and Penaeid prawn diversity
in Digha Coast, Bay of Bengal**

Sanchita Nayak (Tripathy)* and Angsuman Chanda

Research centre in Natural & Applied Sciences

Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Mednapore- 721102, West Bengal, India.

**Email: nayaksanchita 87@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

The family Penaeidae dominated the prawn community of the coastal habitat of Digha, Bay of Bengal. A total of 8,081 individuals, representing twenty-six species of eight genera, were sampled to determine seasonal variation in the relative abundance and species diversity of penaeid prawns. The most abundant species of penaeid prawn was *Parapenaeopsis coromandelica* (12.88%), followed by *Metapenaeus lysianassa* (10.40%), *Helleropenaeopsis sculptilis* (8.74%), *Parapenaeopsis stylifera* (8.02%), *Metapenaeus brevicornis* (5.54%), *Penaeus monodon* (5.41%), *Penaeus indicus* (5.09%), *Metapenaeus hardwickii* (4.59%), and so on. The relative abundance of the species fluctuated seasonally. The Digha coast had the highest species richness during the monsoon season and the lowest during the pre-monsoon period, while the maximum diversity was also recorded during the monsoon season. The socioeconomic status of the inhabitants in the Digha coastal region is heavily reliant on marine fishing, which is one of the most important livelihood opportunities for residents of the Digha coastal belt. The information was collected from selected villages in the Digha coastal region. A random sample of 2,656 respondents was examined. According to FAO guidelines, 30% of the 618 families are above the poverty line, while the rest are below it.

Keywords: *Diversity; Seasonal Abundance; Socio-Economic Status; Livelihood; Fishermen; Digha Coast.*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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**The Triple Threat: Corruption, Governance, and Environmental Degradation in
BIMSTEC Countries**

Sneha Dey*, Priya Mondal and Soumyajit Bhunia

*Department of Economics, Panskura Banamali College (Autonomous), Panskura, Purba Medinipur
Email: snehadey.sn@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Environmental degradation is one of the serious threats in the economy that are being looked in the world today. The rapid carbon emissions are causing greater problems like climate change and global warming. This study is trying to investigate the interplay between democracy, corruption, and environmental degradation across the Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multisectoral and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC) region. Using a panel of seven BIMSTEC countries spanning a period of 20 years (2000-2019), the present study seeks to shed some light to examine the association among political factors, and the environmental degradation. Essentially, the purpose of our study is to analyze the impact of political factors on carbon emission in the economy. We apply fixed effect and random effect estimation technique to analyze this relationship. Our findings suggest that an increase in population density has a positive and significant impact on carbon emissions. Estimation results also affirm that democracy increases carbon emissions. Furthermore, regression results show that that a more politically stable country distribute more carbon emissions across the region. Essentially, our study discloses that the intertwined influences of population growth, democratic governance, and political stability cooperatively intertwine a complex tapestry of carbon emissions, with far-reaching outcomes for the well-being of our ecosystem.

Keywords: *Democracy; Corruption; Political stability; Panel data; BIMSTEC countries.*

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Screening and Characterization of Heterotrophic Nitrifying Bacteria from Carp Culture Ponds for Sustainable Water Quality Management

*Romita Mondal and Kartik Maiti**

*Research centre in Natural & Applied Sciences
Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Mednapore- 721102, West Bengal, India.
Email: kartikmaiti10@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of the aquaculture industry raises significant concerns about the environment, particularly on the nitrogenous waste pollution. Bacteria exhibiting heterotrophic nitrification–aerobic denitrification (HN-AD) ability can remove ammonia along with nitrite and nitrate within the same system. They exhibit enhanced growth and resilience compared to the autotrophic nitrifiers and anaerobic denitrifiers involved in traditional nitrogen removal methods. A bacterial strain, designated as HNF_M1, was isolated from carp ponds and identified as *Pseudomonas qingdaonensis* based on phylogenetic analysis of its 16S rRNA gene sequence. Strain HNF_M1 exhibited highest ammonia removal efficiency, with negligible nitrite accumulation, indicating that nitrogen transformation likely occurred through heterotrophic nitrification integrated with aerobic denitrification. The optimal conditions for achieving maximum nitrification activity by strain HNF_M1 were determined to be a pH of 7.5, temperature of 31 °C, C/N ratio of 10, and shaking speed of 120 rpm. Strain HNF_M1 showed no detectable pathogenicity on the of *Labeo bata*, confirming its bio-safety for aquaculture application. The strain HNF_M1 showing significant potential for bioremediation of ammonia removal in freshwater aquaculture systems.

Keywords: *HN-AD; Pseudomonas sp.; ammonium removal efficiency; bioremediation.*

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Impacts of Climate Change on Human Health and Living in India

Atanu Mitra*

*Tarakali Vidyapith, Mahatabpur, Midnapore, Paschim Medinipur,
West Bengal, India, PIN- 721101*

**Email: mramitra70@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Climate change is drastic from Poles to Tropics. It poses a worldwide threat. Globally, the sustainability of many different sectors is declining due to climate unpredictability. The effects of global climate change from greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) are diverse and potentially very large and probably constitute the most serious long-term environmental issue currently facing India as well as the world. The coastal area as well as urban areas of West Bengal faced various kinds of natural changes. One of the major significant changes is in climatic conditions. The consequences of climate change are far-reaching and multifaceted, impacting natural ecosystems, human societies and the global economy. Key effects are more frequent and severe weather events like severe cyclones, droughts and floods, rising sea levels due to polar ice melt, ocean acidification and shifts in ecosystems and biodiversity. These changes threaten food and water security, increase health risks and exacerbate social inequalities, particularly in vulnerable communities. The paper tries to show the factors and effects of climate dealing with its analysis in the second most densely populated state in India. The paper discusses the factors responsible for climate change in the Bay of Bengal and its effects by studying several parameters rather than focusing on a single factor. The paper shows how the changes are still having a serious impact on influencing lives and living in the region.

Keywords: *Climate change; Cyclones; Coastal ecosystem; De-oxygenation; GHGs; Biodiversity, Human health.*

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Spatio-Temporal Dynamics of Sal (*Shorea robusta*) Forest Cover, Above-Ground Biomass, and Ecosystem Service Valuation: Insights into Livelihood Implications in the Midnapore Forest Division

Pravat Kumar Shit* and Swapna Ghorai

*Department of Geography, Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous),
Midnapore, West Bengal, India.*

* Email: pravatgeo2007@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The present study examines the spatio-temporal dynamics of Sal (*Shorea robusta*) forest cover, above-ground biomass (AGB), and the changing availability of non-timber forest products (NTFPs), highlighting their influence on local livelihoods in the Midnapore Forest Division from 1995 to 2025. The valuation of provisioning ecosystem services (PES) was undertaken using both market price assessment and benefit transfer methods. Biomass was estimated through field-based forest inventory data (BDH method), while carbon stock and CO₂ sequestration were calculated following IPCC guidelines. By integrating satellite imagery, field surveys, and geospatial analysis, the study identified a 35.12% decline in forest cover, accompanied by a 7.32% rise in scrubland and minor alterations in agricultural land use. Mature Sal stands, ranging from 32 to 60 feet in height, were found to sequester about 8.6–12.9 tonnes of carbon per hectare annually, depending on stand density. The degradation of dense forest patches has substantially reduced carbon storage, elevated emissions, and diminished the supply of NTFPs essential to indigenous households. Household surveys among 150 indigenous families across six forest fringe villages revealed a mean annual PES value of INR 6,823 per capita, with socio-economic variables showing a significant influence ($p < 0.05$). The average carbon stock was 87.56 tonnes per hectare, equivalent to 332.48 tonnes of CO₂, valued at about INR 334,247 per hectare. Over the last three decades, forest loss and fragmentation have led to a 12.68% decline in forest-based household income. The findings underscore the urgent need for integrated ecosystem valuation and sustainable forest management strategies.

Keywords: *Sal forest; Above-ground biomass; Ecosystem service valuation; Non-timber forest products; Livelihood implications.*

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**Hemato-Biochemical Responses of Freshwater Air-Breathing Catfish *Clarias batrachus*
to Elevated Water Temperature**

Sukla Das* and Kartik Maiti

*Research centre in Natural & Applied Sciences
Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Mednapore- 721102, West Bengal, India.
Email: sukla5das3@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Global warming has drastically changed the world's climate, affecting the water ecosystems by rising water temperature that possessed a significant influence on aquatic life especially fish. In view of these environmental changes, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the hemato-biochemical responses of the economically important freshwater catfish species *Clarias batrachus* under elevated water temperature. Fish were acclimatized at $26\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 days and experimentally exposed to four different temperatures i.e. 26°C , 29°C , 32°C and 35°C under controlled laboratory conditions. Blood samples were analyzed after 3 days and 15 days of exposure for study the acute and chronic stress response respectively after reaching the assigned temperatures. Results showed that hemoglobin(Hb), red blood cell (RBC), packed cell volume(PCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin(MCH) increased significantly with elevated temperature indicating the increase of cell metabolism. Blood glucose increased, serum cholesterol and low density lipoprotein (LDL) increased after 3 days exposure but decreased after 15 days, high density lipoprotein (HDL) increased, triglyceride (TG) decreased after 3 days of exposure but increased up to 32°C then decreased at 35°C after 15 days of exposure. Very low density lipoprotein (VLDL) decreased after 3 days but increased after 15 days, phospholipid showed an inverse relation with VLDL. Heat stress induced energy-demanding metabolic responses in fish and displayed adaptive physiological changes to counteract the effect of rising temperature. The findings of this study are important for understanding how fish adapt to the elevated water temperature and give insight into prevention and management of stress in this fish species, especially in context of climate change.

Keywords: *Climate change; Water temperature; Thermal stress; Clarias batrachus; hemato-biochemical response.*

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Isolation and identification of Indigenous Sulfur Oxidizing Bacteria from Dumping Yard of Midnapore municipality: Unlocking their Potential as a Replenishing Soil for Agricultural Lands

Anup Jana*, Tanushree Samanta, Sagarika Mukhopadhyay and Suman Kalyan Khanra

*Department of Human Physiology, Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous),
Mednapore- 721102, West Bengal, India.*

**Email: janaanupaa93@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Sulphur cycle is important for maintaining the soil fertility and environmental detoxification. One important aspect of sulphur cycle is microbial oxidation of reduced sulphur compounds into bioavailable forms. Thiosulphate agar media has been used as a selective medium for isolation of five different sulphur-oxidising bacteria— SoB1, SoB2, SoB3, SoB4, and SoB5—from the dumping yard of Midnapore municipality for the current study. The isolates were significantly diverse in physiological and biochemical parameters as found in preliminary screening. Four out of five isolates were found to be Gram-negative where SoB5 was the only gram positive bacteria. Morphological studies identified colonies and cell shapes together with the colours of the colonies where a unique green colour was observed in the strain named SoB2, may be an indicative of pigment synthesis. Comprehensive biochemical assays like catalase, urease, indole, methyl red, Voges-Proskauer, and amylase were used to identify the bacteria and it has been demonstrated that the isolates showed heterogeneous metabolic capabilities. By detecting the sulphate production from sodium thiosulphate using 1% barium chloride (BaCl_2) and 1N hydrochloric acid (HCl), the sulphur oxidation potential was measured spectrophotometrically. A sulphate standard curve was prepared using potassium sulphate (K_2SO_4), against which the absorbance of the unknown was measured at 580 nm. The production of sulphate ranged from 56.0 to 100.66 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ after an incubation period of 7 days. The oxidative potential of SoB1 was found to be maximum and it was further confirmed by extending the incubation period to 15 days. The production of sulphate by SoB1 was increased to 132 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. At the same time, a significant drop in pH (from 8.0 to 6.50) was observed that confirmed sulphur oxidation having an acidifying effect. These findings reveal the metabolic diversity and effectiveness of native sulphur oxidising bacteria of which SoB1, exhibited the highest capacity for acidification and sulphur oxidation. Such findings potentiate the fact that sustainable environmental biotechnology can be made possible by these potent isolates' thus promising applications in sulfur-rich waste bioremediation, biofertilizer formulation, and soil restoration.

Keywords: *Sulfur oxidizing bacteria (SOB); Bioconversion; Thiosulfate oxidation; Sulfate production.*

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**Spatial transformation of land use and land cover and identification of hotspots using
geospatial technology: a case of the major industrial zone of eastern India**

Niladri Das*

Department of Geography, Hiralal Bhakat College, Nalhati, Birbhum

**Email: niladridas123@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Population growth supported by technological development has a strong connection with changes in land use. Activities such as uncontrolled mining, rapid urban growth, industrial expansion, and deforestation are putting pressure on land use and land cover. This study used GIS and statistical techniques to analyze land use and land cover (LULC) changes in the Asansol–Durgapur Development Authority (ADDA) region of eastern India. The accuracy of the LULC maps for each year was checked using the Kappa coefficient. The ADDA region is developing quickly due to industrialization and urbanization, which may lead to environmental problems. Therefore, it is an important area for studying land use change scientifically. The main theme of this study is that land use in an industrial region is not evenly distributed and that the number of change hotspots is increasing over time due to continuous land transformation. The study analyzed three years: 1992, 2007, and 2022. This helps in calculating the rate of land use transition. Hotspots of land use change were identified using spatial autocorrelation methods such as Moran's I and Getis-Ord G_i^* statistics. The results show that natural vegetation decreased from 12% in 1992 to 4% in 2022. Agricultural land also declined from 47% to 38% during the same period. On the other hand, industrial and coal mining areas increased slightly by about 1% between 1992 and 2022. If this trend continues, the landscape will gradually change and may affect the natural environment. The findings of this study can help policymakers develop strategies to reduce the negative environmental impacts of industrial and urban growth in the region.

Keywords: *Land use and land cover, Hotspot, Coldspot, rate of change, Accuracy assessment.*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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From Fields to Fishponds: A Study of Socio-Ecological Vulnerability in Moyna CD Block, West Bengal, India

Subhajit Barman* and Avishek Bhunia

Department of Geography, K.D. College of Commerce and General Studies, Midnapore, Paschim Medinipur, 721101, West Bengal, India.

**Email: subhajitbarman413@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

The rapid and unregulated expansion of fisheries ('VERI') through the illegal conversion of fertile paddy field has emerged as a major ecological and socio-economic concern in the Community Development Block of Moyna, West Bengal. Over the past three decades, cultivable lands have increasingly been transformed into commercial fish ponds in pursuit of immediate economic profit. This unscientific process has resulted in significant environmental degradation and growing ecological vulnerability among the local communities. The present study examines the spatial and socio-ecological impacts of this land-use transformation. The research integrates multiple methodological approaches including Land Use-Land Cover (LULC) change detection using Remote Sensing, GIS, and perception analysis through Focus Group Discussions (FGD) and household surveys. Additionally, an ecological cost-benefit analysis was conducted to evaluate the long-term sustainability of brackish water aquaculture practices in the region. The spatio-temporal analysis of land use and land cover change during 2005–2025 indicates a pronounced shift from traditional agricultural landscapes to aquaculture-dominated land use. Agricultural land experienced the highest loss (89.81%), followed by barren land (62.21%) and vegetated areas (43.25%). In contrast, fisheries exhibited the most significant growth (145.36%), while settlement areas expanded by 94.26%, highlighting increasing anthropogenic pressure and the growing dominance of aquaculture-based economic activities in the region. The findings also reveal that, the unprecedented rate of land conversion deteriorate the soil & water quality and responsible for loss of indigenous species and biodiversity. The study highlights the paradox in which perceived economic benefits from aquaculture are actually generating long-term ecological and livelihood vulnerabilities. By identifying the drivers of land-use change and assessing their environmental and social consequences, the study seeks to provide practical guidance for transforming ecological vulnerability into sustainable community resilience.

Keywords: *VERI, Fishponds; Ecological Vulnerability; Spatio-temporal Analysis; Land Use and Land Cover Change*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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**Assessing the Impact of Rapid Urban Expansion on Vegetation Cover in Kolkata Using
Satellite Imagery**

Sushobhan Majumdar*

*Department of Geography, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Jambani, Bankura, West
Bengal, India*

*Email: sushobhan91@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Rapid urban expansion significantly alters land use and land cover patterns, often leading to the degradation of urban vegetation. This study assesses the impact of accelerated urban growth on vegetation cover in Kolkata using multi-temporal satellite imagery and geospatial techniques. Landsat data spanning the past three decades were analyzed to quantify changes in vegetation distribution and urban built-up areas. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was employed to evaluate vegetation health and density, while supervised classification methods were used to map land use/land cover transitions. The results indicate a substantial decline in dense vegetation, particularly in peri-urban zones, concurrent with a marked increase in built-up land. Urban sprawl was found to be concentrated along major transportation corridors and newly developed residential and commercial clusters. Statistical analysis reveals a strong inverse relationship between built-up expansion and vegetation cover, highlighting the environmental consequences of unplanned urbanization. The findings underscore the need for sustainable urban planning strategies, including the preservation of green spaces and the integration of ecological considerations into development policies. This research demonstrates the effectiveness of remote sensing and GIS tools in monitoring urban ecological transformations and provides valuable insights for policymakers and urban planners seeking to balance development with environmental sustainability.

Keywords: *Urban expansion; Ecological Transformations; NDVI; Vegetation Health; Vegetation Density*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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Water to Plate: Comprehending a Potential Threat to Human Health

Pradyut Bera and Mrinal Mandal*

Department of Geography, Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University, Purulia-723104, West Bengal

**Email: mrinal-mandal@skbu.ac.in*

ABSTRACT

Diversity in food culture is a unique characteristic of India, which caters to a total of 17.94% fish-product consumers. Fish is enriched with different types of vitamins, fatty acids, omega-3, minerals, etc., and is very fond of non-vegetarian people, especially in Bengal, with a belief that consuming fish can lead to good health. A gradual increase in demand for fish triggers the growth of the aquaculture system at an industry scale by introducing supplements for fast growth rate within a short time as a key technique of the blue revolution. Freshwater aquaculture in coastal Bengal, India, has been a new venture for the economy for the last decade. The produced fish (mainly Indian Major Carps: *C. catla*, *L. rohita*, and *C. mrigala*) were collected (n = 12) purposively from aquaculture ponds, primarily stored and transferred using an ice-box, and finally preserved in a -20 °C refrigerator before analysis in Inductively Coupled Plasma – Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP – OES) following internationally recognized guidelines. The analysis portrayed that the produced fish was contaminated with different toxic heavy metal/loids, e.g., Zn, Cd, As, Pb, etc., among which, some are also identified as carcinogens by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). The concentration of those toxic elements is basically the effect of biomagnification in fish muscle, which was found to be recorded as higher than the maximum permissible limit as suggested by the World Health Organization, and can travel towards the upper trophic level through long-term continuous consumption. The Estimated Daily Intake, followed by Total Hazard Quotient and Target Cancer Risk, inferred that the prolonged consumption of such contaminated fish is of enough risk for human health.

Keywords: *Contaminants; Human health; Health indices; Carcinogen; Hazard quotient.*

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**A Pressure-State-Response Framework Based Evaluation of Watershed Condition and
Environmental Stress in the Damodar River Basin**

Md Hasanuzzaman* and Pravat Kumar Shit

*PG Department of Geography, Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore,
West Bengal, India.*

**Email: hasan20geo@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

River basins across the industrializing world are bearing the cumulative weight of decades of unchecked anthropogenic pressure, and few illustrate this crisis as starkly as India's Damodar River. Flowing through the mineral-rich heartlands of Jharkhand before spreading into West Bengal's densely populated plains, the Damodar has long been synonymous with industrial ambition and ecological sacrifice. This study adopts the Pressure-State-Response (PSR) framework a structured, causality-based diagnostic tool developed by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) to systematically appraise the health of this critically stressed watershed. By disaggregating the basin's environmental condition into the stresses imposed upon it (Pressure), the ecological and hydrological reality those stresses have produced (State), and the institutional and community measures deployed in response (Response), the analysis reveals a system under severe strain. Water quality in the industrial midstream has deteriorated well beyond national drinking standards, biodiversity has contracted sharply, and hydrological integrity has been fundamentally altered by a cascade of dams and barrages. While regulatory frameworks and infrastructure investments represent meaningful steps forward, they remain insufficient in scale and consistency to match the pace of ongoing degradation. This paper argues that meaningful recovery demands not incremental policy adjustment but a transformed model of integrated, adaptive watershed governance.

Keywords: *Pressure-State-Response Framework; Watershed; Environmental Stress; Ecological risk assessment; Damodar River basin*

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**Classification of Nature of Elephant Attack on Human-Elephant Conflict Using
Machine Learning Technique**

Arup Das*
Department of Computer Science
Raja N.L Khan women's College,
Midnapore , West Bengal
**Email: arup@rnlkwc.ac.in*

ABSTRACT

With the advancement of human civilization and more instances of deforestation, humans are aggressively sharing land and resources of wild life, leading to frequent and often fatal human wild life conflict. Amongst all of these, human-elephant conflict is most critical concern to our society, as any human-elephant conflict results havoc either in terms of financial or life loss. The situation is similar all over the world here in case of West Bengal, India it's a severe issue. As Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) is becoming a revolutionary tool in most of the problem solving domain so in the field of wild life ecology it can also play a path breaking role. Artificial intelligence (AI) can help us to understand animal behaviour and conservation strategies. This paper focuses on AI driven approaches to understand nature of attack and important factors to the region of west Midnapore.

Keywords: *Human-elephant conflict; Elephant Attack classification; Artificial Intelligence.*

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Phytotherapeutic Potential of *Calotropis gigantea* in Controlling Ectoparasites of Ornamental Goldfish

Bidipta Roy and Monjit Paul

Department of Biological Sciences (Fisheries Science), Midnapore City College

Email: monjit.paul@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Ectoparasitic infestations represent a major constraint in ornamental fish culture, particularly in intensively reared goldfish (*Carassius auratus*), where protozoan, monogenean, and crustacean parasites cause severe morbidity and mortality. The present study evaluated the antiparasitic efficacy of ethanolic leaf extract of *Calotropis gigantea* against mixed ectoparasitic infections under controlled laboratory conditions. Infected goldfish were exposed to six concentrations of the extract (1–25 mg L⁻¹) for 15 days in a completely randomized design. Parasitological assessment, mortality analysis, and log-dose regression modelling were performed to determine dose–response relationships and effective concentrations (EC₅₀ and EC₉₀). Results demonstrated a clear concentration-dependent reduction in parasite intensity. The highest antiparasitic efficacy (97.95 ± 1.12%) was recorded at 25 mg L⁻¹, with a corresponding reduction in mean parasite intensity from 69.62 ± 11.60 in the control to 3.87 ± 1.45. Mortality showed an inverse relationship with treatment concentration, decreasing from 90.00 ± 5.00% in the control to 5.00 ± 0.00% at 25 mg L⁻¹. Regression analysis revealed strong dose–response relationships (R² = 0.889–0.948; p ≤ 0.002). Among parasites, *Trichodina* spp. exhibited the highest sensitivity (EC₅₀ = 4.62 ± 2.77 mg L⁻¹), whereas *Lernaea* spp. showed comparatively lower sensitivity (EC₅₀ = 11.37 ± 3.41 mg L⁻¹). The findings indicate that *C. gigantea* leaf extract possesses significant broad-spectrum antiparasitic activity and markedly improves host survival. Concentrations between 20–25 mg L⁻¹ may represent an effective therapeutic window for managing mixed ectoparasitic infections in goldfish. This study supports the potential of plant-based phytotherapeutics as sustainable alternatives to conventional chemotherapeutics in ornamental aquaculture.

Keywords: *Calotropis gigantea*; Goldfish; Ectoparasites; Dose–response; EC₅₀; Phytotherapy; Ornamental aquaculture.

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**Assessment of Water Quality and Ecological Status of Historic Man-Made Water Bodies
in Bishnupur, West Bengal, India**

Aparupa Haldar* and Sujoy Midya

*PG Department of Zoology, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore,
West Bengal, India.*

Email: aparupahaldar95@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Freshwater ecosystems are increasingly threatened by anthropogenic pressures associated with rapid urbanization, necessitating integrated assessments to ensure ecological sustainability. This study evaluates the water quality and ecological status of seven historic freshwater impoundments in Bishnupur, Jamuna Bandh, Kalindi Bandh, Gantait Bandh, Poka Bandh, Krishna Bandh, Shyam Bandh, and Lal Bandh—constructed during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries under the Malla dynasty. Thirty-five surface water samples were collected, and zooplankton communities were sampled using a 0.5-mm mesh plankton net. Physicochemical parameters analysed included pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), turbidity, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chlorophyll-a, and total phosphorus (TP). Concentrations of selected heavy metals (Fe, Zn, Cd, Pb, Ni, and Cr) and major ions (Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , and NO_3^-) were also determined. Overall water quality was assessed using the Water Quality Index (WQI), while Cluster Analysis (CA) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) were employed to identify spatial variability and potential pollution sources. Zooplankton assemblages were dominated by Copepoda, Ostracoda, and Protozoa, indicating spatial variation in trophic conditions among the reservoirs. WQI results classified most water bodies as exhibiting poor to very poor water quality, with trophic states ranging from mesotrophic to eutrophic. Multivariate analyses identified nutrient enrichment, organic loading, and metal contamination—largely driven by anthropogenic activities—as the primary factors contributing to water quality degradation. These findings highlight the vulnerability of historically significant freshwater systems and underscore the need for continuous monitoring and targeted management strategies to preserve their ecological integrity.

Keywords: *Water quality assessment; Zooplankton; Water Quality Index (WQI); Heavy Metal Index; Trophic State Index.*

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**Assessment of Lead-Induced Biochemical Stress in the Soil Collembola *Xenylla welchi*
Folsom, 1916**

Priyanka Sarangi¹, Partha Pratim Chakravorty^{1*} and Bhabatosh Das²

¹PG Department of Zoology, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Gope Palace,
Medinipur (Affiliated to Vidyasagar University), West Bengal -721102, India

²Translational Health Science and Technology Institute, NCR Biotech Cluster, 3rd Milestone,
Faridabad-Gurugram, India

Email: priyankasarangi18@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Heavy metal contamination in soil ecosystems is a growing environmental concern due to rapid industrialization and the disposal of coal fly ash containing toxic metals. Among these, lead (Pb) is particularly hazardous because of its persistence, bioaccumulation potential, and toxicity to soil organisms. The present study aimed to assess lead-induced biochemical stress responses in the soil collembola *Xenylla welchi* (Folsom, 1916) and evaluate its potential as a biomarker of soil pollution. Fly ash-contaminated soil was collected from the Kolaghat Thermal Power Plant, West Bengal, India, and heavy metal composition was determined using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS). Lead showed the highest concentration among the analyzed metals and was therefore selected for toxicity evaluation. Acute toxicity tests determined the 24-hour LC₅₀ value of lead acetate on *X. welchi* as 2653.23 mg/kg. Sublethal concentrations were used to analyze biochemical responses after 1, 3, and 7 days of exposure. Biomarkers including glutathione (GSH), glutathione-S-transferase (GST), acetylcholinesterase (AChE), and metallothionein (MT) were measured from whole-body homogenates. Results showed decreased GSH and AChE activities, indicating oxidative stress and neurotoxicity, while GST activity increased initially but declined after prolonged exposure. Metallothionein levels increased during later exposure periods, suggesting metal detoxification. These findings indicate that *X. welchi* is a sensitive bioindicator for assessing Pb-induced stress in soil ecosystems.

Keywords: Heavy metal; Collembola; Oxidative stress; Ecotoxicology; Environment

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Microplastic Pollution in Freshwater Ecosystems: Insights from Commercial Bivalves of Undivided Medinipur District

Sumana Mahato* and Sujoy Midya,

P.G. Department of Zoology, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore, West Bengal-721102, India.

Email: sumanamahato0@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Aquatic ecosystems are increasingly degraded by anthropogenic pollution, one of them is microplastic (MPs) emerging as a prevalent and persistent contaminant affecting freshwater biodiversity and ecosystem services. Bivalves, due to their filter-feeding behaviour, ecological importance and socioeconomic value for rural communities, serve as effective bioindicators of aquatic environmental health. The present study assesses the concentration and distribution of MPs in commercially important freshwater bivalve species collected from East Medinipur, West Medinipur and Jhargram district of West Bengal, India, regions where inland fisheries contribute significantly to local livelihoods and food security. A total of 150 bivalve specimens were collected from local markets for analysis. The selected bivalves had body weight ranging from approximately 24g to 58g and lengths between 4.5 cm and 8 cm. From 720.6 g of dissected tissue (including gut and muscle), 1027 MP particles were isolated, creating an average of 1.42 MP particles per gram of tissue. The MPs were categorized by colour- predominantly red, followed by black, blue, green and white and also by morphology, including fibres, fragments and sheets. Visual identification under stereomicroscope and polymer characterization via Raman micro spectroscopy indicated that the highest MP abundance occurred in bivalves collected from Jhargram district, while the lowest levels were recorded in those from East Medinipur district. The findings highlight the extent of plastic pollution in waterbodies, potential to compromise bivalve biodiversity and the sustainability of rural livelihood dependent on these resources.

Keywords: *Freshwater bivalves; Filter-feeding; Microplastic; Rural livelihood; Raman Spectroscopy.*

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Fish diversity, habitat ecology and their conservation of Dulung river, Jhargram

Sudipta Pratihar*

*Research Centre in Natural and Applied Sciences, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College
(Autonomous), Midnapore, West Bengal-721102, India.*

*Email: sudipta442@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Present study has conducted on species diversity, habitat ecology, distribution and conservation of Ichthyofauna in Dulung River, Jhargram, West Bengal. The fish species richness and habitat ecology showed good relationship and water depth, dissolve oxygen and pH were found the most important variable in shaping fish assemblage. We identified 20 fish species and order Cypriniformes is the maximum fish groups of the riverine habitat are noted. Fish samples and water samples were collected from four sampling stations spread along the upstream, mid stream and down streams habitat. Cyprinids were the most dominant group represents by 15 species belonging to 8 genera, where as Bagridae represents 6 species from 3 genera. The distribution of fish shows that about 10% species were common to all sites. Out of 20 species 15 categorised as low risk 2 as vulnerable and 3 as endangered. Our study shows that the River Dulung supports considerable diversity of the fish and is essential for conservation of about 25% species in the habitat. We assessed that in this river approximate 100% fish are food fish and about 2-3% are both food and ornamental value. But recently fish production abruptly decreases day by day for severe anthropogenic and industrial River pollution. This poster highlights the crucial needs for sustainable management, habitat restoration and strict enforcement of fishing regulations to preserve the aquatic heritage of West Bengal.

Keywords: *Species diversity; Habitat ecology; River pollution.*

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**Geospatial Multi-Criteria Framework for Sustainable EV Charging Infrastructure
Planning: A Case Study of Ayodhya**

Bhavya Mangla, Devansh Negi, Shruti and Sudipta Hore*

*Symbiosis Institute of Geoinformatics
Symbiosis International University (Deemed University)
Pune, Maharashtra-411016, India*

*Email: bm.bhavya.09@gmail.com / devnegi8192@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The global transition toward electric mobility is a critical component of climate mitigation and sustainable urban development strategies. Efficient spatial planning of Electric Vehicle Charging Stations (EVCS) is essential to support low-carbon transportation systems while ensuring accessibility, environmental compatibility, and infrastructural feasibility. This study presents a GIS-based Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) framework for optimized EV charging infrastructure planning in Ayodhya. The research integrates the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), Weighted Overlay Analysis, and ROC–AUC validation to develop a scientifically robust and reliable suitability model. Key spatial parameters considered include land use/land cover, population density, proximity to road networks, power substations, fuel stations, environmental constraints such as water bodies, and air quality indicators. Each thematic layer was standardized and reclassified into suitability classes to ensure comparability. Criterion weights were determined using AHP, with consistency ratios evaluated to maintain logical coherence in decision-making. The weighted overlay process generated a composite suitability index categorizing the study area into high, moderate, and low suitability zones for EVCS installation. Model performance was validated using Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis, confirming the predictive accuracy of the spatial framework. The proposed approach functions as a decision-support system for policymakers and urban planners, facilitating data-driven strategies for sustainable mobility infrastructure. The study highlights the role of geospatial technologies in enabling climate-responsive urban planning and accelerating the transition toward low-carbon cities.

Keywords: *Electric Vehicle Charging Stations (EVCS); Sustainable Urban Planning; Climate Mitigation; Spatial Optimization; ROC–AUC Validation.*

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Assessment of agricultural land suitability using integrated AHP-TOPSIS and Machine learning techniques: A case study of Pusad Taluka, Yavatmal district, India

Pallavi Bange, Akash Jadhav, Yukta Salvi and Sandipan Das*

*Symbiosis Institute of Geoinformatics
Symbiosis International University (Deemed University)
Pune, Maharashtra-411016, India
Email: sandipanraj2002@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Agricultural land suitability assessment is vital for sustainable land use planning, particularly in regions facing growing demands for food production and natural resource optimization. This study introduces an approach which combines the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), and machine learning (ML) techniques to assess agricultural land suitability in Pusad Taluka, Yavatmal District, Maharashtra. Geospatial datasets including slope, soil texture, soil pH, organic carbon, cation exchange capacity (CEC), land use/land cover (LULC), temperature, and rainfall were used to generate thematic layers. AHP was applied to derive the relative importance of each criterion through expert-based pairwise comparisons, while TOPSIS was used to rank land parcels based on their proximity to an ideal solution, generating a suitability classification map. To further enhance the reliability of the classification, machine learning classifiers K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), and Random Forest (RF) were implemented. The dataset underwent preprocessing to remove null values and convert categorical suitability classes into numerical values. An 80:20 train-test split was used for model training and evaluation. Model performance was assessed using accuracy, recall, F1-score, confusion matrices, and ROC curves. The classification accuracies achieved were 89% for KNN, 91.9% for DT, and 93% for RF, with Random Forest outperforming the others. Visualization of model results using confusion matrix heatmaps and bar charts provided comparative insights. The integrated AHP-TOPSIS-ML framework effectively captured spatial heterogeneity and expert insights while leveraging data-driven classification, offering a robust methodology for informed land resource planning. Results indicated that 27.4% of the land (103,837.84 ha) is highly suitable, 62.5% moderately suitable, and 2.3% less suitable. This approach supports climate-resilient, sustainable agricultural development in semi-arid agroecological zones (Negussie et al., 2024; Sathiyamurthi et al., 2024; Malczewski, 1999).

Keywords: Agricultural land suitability; AHP; TOPSIS; GIS; remote sensing; machine learning;

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Environmental chemistry of coastal wetlands and its implications for aquaculture sustainability in Nayachar Island, West Bengal

Sumita Deshmukh¹, Partha Bandyopadhyay² and Sujoy Midya^{1*}

¹ PG Department of Zoology, Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Gope Palace, Medinipur (Affiliated to Vidyasagar University), West Bengal-721102, India

² Finray Biotech Pvt. Ltd., 613, Fortune Business Hub, 6th Floor, Science City Road, Sola, Ahmedabad-380060, India

Email: sujoy.midya@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Coastal wetlands act as natural buffers against pollution and play a crucial role in sustaining aquaculture; however, increasing anthropogenic activities have significantly altered their environmental chemistry. The present study investigates the impact of pollution-induced changes in water quality on shrimp aquaculture in Nayachar Island, located in the Hooghly–Haldi estuarine system of West Bengal. Seasonal assessment of key physicochemical parameters and nutrient concentrations was conducted to evaluate their influence on aquaculture performance. Results indicate that elevated nutrient loads and deteriorating water quality are closely associated with reduced productivity. These findings highlight the chemical dynamics of polluted wetland waters and their implications for aquatic ecosystem health. Correlation analysis between water quality parameters and aquaculture output demonstrates the necessity for continuous environmental monitoring and pollution control strategies. The study emphasizes the importance of integrating principles of environmental chemistry with sustainable aquaculture management to mitigate pollution impacts and enhance ecosystem resilience. This work provides baseline data for environmental monitoring by addressing pollution pathways that affect aquatic food resources. The outcomes support the ecosystem-based management and bioremediation approaches to ensure long-term sustainability of wetland-dependent aquaculture systems under increasing anthropogenic pressure.

Keywords: *Environmental chemistry; water pollution; coastal wetlands; shrimp aquaculture; nutrient dynamics; ecosystem health; sustainable management*

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**Sustainable Urbanization in the Fragile Himalayan Frontier: Insights from Western
Himachal Pradesh**

Sanchita Barik* and Arnab Kundu

*Department of Geo-Informatics, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Bankura
University, Bankura, West Bengal, India*

**Email: bariksanchita36@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of the dynamic urban growth patterns in five ecologically sensitive towns of Western Himachal Pradesh: Chamba, Kangra, Dharamshala, Dalhousie, and Bharmour. Utilizing high-resolution Sentinel-2A MSI satellite imagery and state-of-the-art Digital Elevation Models (DEM), the research examines the intricate interplay between topographical constraints and anthropogenic expansion through the application of advanced spatial indices, including Land Use/Land Cover (LULC), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), and Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI). The findings reveal a highly heterogeneous growth pattern, primarily dictated by the unique altitude and accessibility characteristics of each town. Dharamshala and Kangra exhibit the highest rates of urbanization, driven by a thriving tourism industry and administrative functions, which have resulted in significant vegetation loss and increased built-up density. Conversely, Chamba and Dalhousie show a more moderate and regulated expansion, while Bharmour remains significantly constrained by its rugged high-altitude terrain. The study identifies a critical correlation between the uncontrolled urban sprawl and the alarming degradation of local ecosystems, specifically through habitat fragmentation and altered moisture regimes. The research concludes that the current growth trajectories in these Himalayan towns necessitate the implementation of an integrated, multidisciplinary planning framework. By balancing the economic drivers, such as tourism, with robust environmental conservation strategies, the study provides actionable recommendations for policymakers to foster sustainable urban development and enhance climate resilience in this fragile and ecologically sensitive Himalayan landscape.

Keywords: *Himalayan Urbanization; Topographical Constraints; Ecological Sensitivity; Sustainable Development; Climate Resilience; Geo-Spatial Analysis.*

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**Impact of Climate Change on the Daily Lives of Slum Dwellers in Midnapore Town,
West Bengal**

Prabhat Bhattacharya

Department of Geography,

Sukumar Sengupta Mahavidyalaya, Keshpur, Paschim Medinipur – 721150

Email: bhattacharyapra86@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Climate change poses disproportionate risks to urban poor populations, particularly slum dwellers who live in environmentally fragile and infrastructural deficient areas. This study examines the impact of climate change on the daily lives of slum dwellers in Midnapore town. Adopting a mixed-methods approach, the research integrates quantitative household surveys with qualitative interviews and field observations to capture both measurable vulnerabilities and lived experiences. A structured questionnaire was administered to 650 households across selected slum clusters to assess exposure to heat stress, water scarcity, health risks, income instability, and housing damage. In addition, in-depth interviews with community members, local leaders, and municipal representatives were conducted to understand coping strategies, adaptive practices, and institutional responses. Quantitative findings indicate a significant increase in heat-related illnesses, and irregular water supply over the past decade, with more than two-thirds of respondents reporting livelihood disruptions during extreme weather events. Women, elderly residents, and informal workers were found to be particularly vulnerable due to limited mobility, precarious employment, and inadequate access to healthcare. Qualitative insights reveal that climate stressors intensify existing socio-economic inequalities, forcing households to adopt short-term coping mechanisms such as borrowing, migration, and reduced food consumption. Despite some municipal interventions, gaps persist in early warning dissemination, drainage infrastructure, and climate-resilient housing. The study underscores that climate change impacts in Midnapore's slums are not merely environmental but deeply social and economic in nature. It highlights the urgent need for localized adaptation planning, inclusive urban governance, and community-based resilience strategies to protect vulnerable populations. By combining statistical evidence with lived narratives, the research contributes to a nuanced understanding of climate vulnerability in small urban centers of eastern India.

Keywords: *Climate change; Urban slums; Vulnerability; Adaptation strategies; Heat stress*

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Indigenous Knowledge on Cyclone Resilience and Cognitive Patterns among Native Communities of the Ganjam Coast, Odisha

Monalisa Barik Parida^{1*}, and Swapna Ghorai²

¹*Department of Geography, Bankura University, Bankura-722155, West Bengal*

²*Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Gope Palace, Medinipur-721102, West Bengal India*

Email: paridadd@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The Indian subcontinent with its geographical uniqueness is one of the most cyclone vulnerable region in the world. Of all the severe cyclones that make landfall on the eastern coast of India, most of them devastate the Odisha coastline. Statistical analysis of the occurrence of cyclonic storms shows a declining trend, though the incidence of severe cyclonic storms is on the rise owing to climate variability due to global warming. The Ganjam district of Odisha being the 6th most cyclone vulnerable region of the world, has a robust integrated disaster management system to cope with this natural hazard. The disaster management system of the state has developed on the indigenous knowledge of the local community on cyclone resilience and coping mechanism. The fishing community and the kewda cultivators form the economic backbone of this district and thus, the government plays a major role in safeguarding these people during the calamities by issuing timely alerts, providing shelter and relief, and post-cyclone welfare schemes. In this study, the coping mechanism of the fishing community and the kewda cultivators are thoroughly examined highlighting the diversification of their livelihood. The remarkable adaptability of the indigenous people in designing settlements with wind brake plantation along the coast, cultivation of crops that mature during non-cyclonic period and practice of short-term migration are discussed here. The resilience and cogitation pattern of these indigenous people serve as a basis for the development of cyclone disaster management model across other states in India.

Keywords: *Indigenous Knowledge; Resilience; Coping Mechanism; Adaptability; Cogitation Pattern*

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Shell Microstructure and Biomineralization in *Lingula anatina* (Brachiopoda: Lingulidae): Insights from SEM, EDS, XRD and Raman Analyses

Prabad Pratim Pal^{1*} and Sudipta Kumar Ghorai²

¹*Coastal Environmental Studies Research Centre of Egra SSB College affiliated to Vidyasagar University, Medinipur, West Bengal, India*

²*Ramananda College, Bishnupur, Bankura, WB, India*

**Email:prabadp1205@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

The shell of *Lingula anatina*, a modern representative of one of the earliest brachiopod lineages, displays a distinctive organophosphatic biomineralization system in which inorganic minerals are intricately integrated with organic matrices to enhance structural performance. In this study, the shell's microstructure, elemental composition, and mineralogical characteristics were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and Raman spectroscopy. SEM observations revealed clear regional variation in shell architecture, ranging from densely packed fibrous laminae to more porous and reticulated layers, suggesting functional differentiation that contributes to both mechanical strength and flexibility. Elemental analysis indicated that the shell matrix is primarily composed of calcium phosphate in the form of fluorapatite, accompanied by trace elements including magnesium, manganese, and iron. Mineralogical analyses using XRD and Raman spectroscopy further confirmed the presence of crystalline fluorapatite and calcite, along with substantial amorphous components. These amorphous phases are likely associated with organic constituents such as chitin, proteins, and glycosaminoglycans that play key roles in biomineralization. Overall, the results demonstrate that *Lingula* shells possess a complex hierarchical structure combining organic and inorganic materials, reflecting an evolutionarily conserved strategy that provides durability, environmental adaptability, and controlled biomineral formation.

Keywords: *Lingula anatina; Brachiopoda; Shell microstructure; Biomineralization; Fluorapatite; Ramanspectroscopy.*

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Combating Desertification in Rajasthan: The Role of Remote Sensing and GIS

Anupam Kundu* and Arnab Kundu

*Department of Geo-Informatics, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Bankura
University, Bankura, West Bengal, India*

**Email: anupamkundu424@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Rajasthan is the largest state in India but is found in the northwest of the nation with its capital based at Jaipur or the Pink City. Being regarded as one of the most important components of Thar Desert, the state is known by its magnificent forts, palaces, and lively culture, folk dancing, and courage of such historic rulers as Maharana Pratap. The conversion of productive land to dry and unproductive land is known as desertification; it was mainly used in arid and semi-arid regions. Some of the causes that have led to this are deforestation, over grazing, poor agricultural farming and climatic changes. This problem is present in many Asian and African countries such as India, especially in such states as Gujarat and Rajasthan. The United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification adopts a global approach in dealing with land degradation on a global scale. The Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and satellite imagery used in remote sensing are widely used in order to measure the effects of desertification. The images of the Earth surface are taken by satellites, and GIS is employed to save, analyze, and prepare the maps of the information. The combination gives very useful information about land degradation and aids in planning and implementing restoration projects. The satellite images can also be useful in making decisions and conducting studies especially when using the NASA data. In order to monitor desertification, the machine-learning procedure is utilized, with the following parameters being followed: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), Fractional Vegetation Cover (FVC), aridity index, soil moisture, soil texture, elevation, crop yield, and Evapotranspiration (ETa). Such analysis of data will permit the model to determine the risk areas according to desertification to make effective, accurate, and useful strategies to control the land degradation.

Keywords: *Deforestation; Overgrazing; Climate Change; Machine Learning; Satellite Imagery.*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
Government of West Bengal

Histological Alterations of Vital Organs in *Cirrhinus mrigala* at Different Acclimation Temperatures and Exposed To Higher Temperature.

Tilak Das* and Dibyendu Das

*P.G. Department of Zoology, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous)
Midnapore, West Bengal-721102, India.*

**Email: drtilakdas1@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

The present study investigates histological alterations in vital organs-kidney, liver, and gill-of *Cirrhinus mrigala* advanced fingerlings under different thermal conditions. The fish were acclimated at temperatures of 26°C (control), 31°C, 33°C, and 36°C for 30 days, and subsequently exposed to Critical Thermal Maxima (CTMax) ($40.25 \pm 0.17^\circ\text{C}$) and Critical Thermal Minima (CTMin) ($12.12 \pm 0.07^\circ\text{C}$). The temperature was gradually increased or decreased from 26°C at a rate of 0.3°C per minute to determine the thermal tolerance limits. Histological observations revealed that fish acclimated at 26°C, 31°C, and 33°C maintained normal histoarchitecture in the examined organs. In contrast, fish acclimated at 36°C and those exposed to CTMax and CTMin exhibited significant pathological alterations, including damage to gill lamellae, hepatic hypertrophy in the liver, and renal hyperplasia in the kidney. These findings indicate that elevated acclimation temperatures and abrupt thermal stress can induce severe histopathological changes in *C. mrigala*. The results highlight the potential impacts of thermal stress on fish health and emphasize the importance of monitoring environmental temperature fluctuations. This study provides valuable insights for the sustainable management of *C. mrigala* aquaculture, particularly under the current climate change scenario.

Keywords: *Cirrhinus mrigala*; Histology; Temperature acclimation; CTMax; CTMin.

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Assessment of wetland health and Ecological risk for restoration Strategies to sustainable livelihoods of Murshidabad district, West Bengal, India

Subhasis Das^{1,2*} and Pravat Kumar Shit²

¹*Department of Geography, Narajole Raj College, West Bengal India.*

²*PG Department of Geography, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore, West Bengal, India.*

Email:subhasidas4592@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The wetland ecosystem has significant contribution for protecting environmental challenges, and answer the questions food and water crisis in the contemporary context. But, the degradation of health condition of the wetland ecosystem has threats for the survival of living organisms as well as human society. The assessment of wetland ecosystem health in the fourteen selected wetlands of Murshidabad district, West Bengal contribute ecological process that primarily benefits local community and the economy of the district abroad. Our research has unfolded from different dimensions and uses statistical, remote sensing and geographical information system methods, through the investigation in the perspective- spatial - temporal change of wetland area, water pollution status, ecosystem services identification and valuation, ecological risk and wetland health status. The result finds that shrinkage of wetland area and continuous increasing water pollution cause for habitat loss and alteration, and decrease in ecosystem service production. The natural and anthropogenetic ecological risk factors changes in landscape pattern, structure and fragmentation, that creates livelihood vulnerability at the wetland dependent communities. The livelihoods dependency on wetland resources has significantly decreased and they choose alternative activities for living. Finally, the study identifies households' dependency trends and management behaviours of local communities for designing road map towards the management and restoration of wetland. Therefore, the findings of this study are crucial for policy makers and planner's to implement wetland management plans at the ground level.

Keywords: *Wetland Health; ecological risk; Water Quality Index; Wetland Restoration Pathways; Remote Sensing Technology*

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**Household Economic Dependency on Non-Timber Forest Products for Livelihood in the
Dry Deciduous Sal Forest Landscape: Insights from West Bengal, India**

Soumen Bisui* and Pravat Kumar Shit

*PG Department of Geography, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College
(Autonomous), Midnapore, West Bengal, India.*

Email: bisui.soumengeo@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Non-Timber Forest Products (NTFPs) play a vital role in sustaining livelihoods in forest-dependent rural areas where agricultural productivity and wage employment are limited. The Jangal Mahal region of West Bengal, characterized by dry deciduous Sal forests and a large tribal population, shows strong dependence on forest resources. This study examines the extent of household economic dependence on NTFPs and identifies the key determinants influencing such reliance. A multistage sampling method was used to survey 540 households from 50 villages in Paschim Medinipur and Jhargram districts between July 2019 and May 2023. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and Focus Group Discussions. The results indicate that NTFPs contribute 38.74% of total annual household income, followed by wage labour (27.91%) and agriculture (21.65%). Major NTFPs include Sal leaves, Mahua, Kendu leaves, honey, and mushrooms. Regression analysis shows that caste, livestock ownership, and low household income significantly influence NTFP dependence.

Keywords: *Non-Timber Forest Products (NTFPs); Livelihood dependence; Forest-based income; ANOVA; Forest-dependent communities.*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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Himalayan Glacier Retreat and Its Consequences: A Comprehensive Analysis of the Dhauldhara Range Glaciers

Debasish Karmakar* and Arnab Kundu

Department of Geo-Informatics, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Bankura

University, Bankura, West Bengal, India

Email: debasishkarmakar444@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Glaciers play a very vital role in the cryosphere of the earth and are very sensitive to climatic changes. This has seen global glaciers disappearing at an alarming rate in the past few decades such as in the Himalayas, Alps, Andes, Alaska, Greenland and the Antarctica. This massive shrinkage has led to ice-depleting, glaciers thinning and flow dynamics rearrangement to a considerable impact on the snow-covered and high-altitude environs. These changes are causing rise in sea level, changes in river discharge, shortage of water and ecological imbalance in mountainous areas. The retreat of Himalayan glaciers in India has also been observed to occur in a continuous manner as a result of increase in temperature and alterations in snowfall patterns. The glaciers are feeding large rivers and this sustains agriculture, hydropower generation and domestic water supply to millions of people. Glacier thinning and the growth of glacial lakes have become a concern with regard to the water security and glacier threats. The current report is concerned with the Dhauldhara Range and the glaciers around it in the Chamba District of Himachal Pradesh. The research with an interdisciplinary geospatial methodology indicates that the size of the glaciers and quantifiable lowering of the surface gradually declined over the duration of research. The dwindling accumulation areas and growing ablation areas are depicted in the glacier zone mapping and the Equilibrium Line Altitude (ELA) is enlarged and the Accumulation Area Ratio (AAR) values depict an adverse mass balance state. Speed analysis on the surface shows that there is more ice movement in the upper accumulation zones and less in the glacier ends. In sum, the glaciers of the Dhauldhara Range are experiencing active erosion and retreat, and active change, mainly due to the increase in temperature and climatic variability. Such results point out the necessity of regional evaluations and climate change reduction measures to be more detailed and elaborate to meet the challenges caused by glacier recession in the Himalayan area.

Keywords: *Glacier retreat; Climate change; Himalayan glaciers; Glacier dynamics; Water security; Geospatial analysis.*

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Geospatial Approach to Landslide Risk Assessment in the Himalayan Region of India

Subhajit Pal* and Arnab Kundu

*Department of Geo-Informatics, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Bankura
University, Bankura, West Bengal, India
Email: subhajitpal7029@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

In the global scene, landslides are a major hazard that causes 17 percent of the disaster related deaths. The number of those who die annually is more than 4,000 and economic losses are more than 20 billion worldwide. The Himalayan region in India contributes to about 15 percent of the total number of deaths occasioned by landslides in the country. Himachal Pradesh is at a major risk, 45 percent of the state is prone to landslides, with the major part being in the Chamba and Kangra districts, because of the steep slopes, the unstable geological situations, and constant tectonic activity with the heavy rainfall. In order to overcome this difficulty, the study designs a Landslide Susceptibility Mapping (LSM) system with the help of Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS). The satellite imagery can be used to follow the terrain, vegetation development, rain, and surface conditions, whereas the GIS can be used to analyze the intricate associations between geological, hydrological, and human systems spatially. The data set comprises landslide inventory points and other variables, which are elevation, slope, aspect, profile curvature, geomorphology, topographic wetness index (TWI), stream power index (STI), drainage density, geology, lithology, rainfall, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), land use/land cover (LULC), and road, drainage and lineament distances. The study compared ANOVA Analytic Hierarchy Process, or AHP, techniques to machine learning algorithms, such as the Random Forest (RF) and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The combination of machine learning approaches and geospatial data enhanced the precision of hazard forecasting as it created a consistent base of an expert. The models showed a definite capability of determining high-risk regions and defining the smaller-risk regions. The high-resolution maps are very important in helping State Disaster Management Authorities (SDMA) and urban planners to design early warning system and sustainable land-use plans to safeguard the vulnerable communities.

Keywords: *Landslide Susceptibility Mapping (LSM); Machine Learning (ML); Disaster Risk Mitigation; Remote Sensing (RS); Geographic Information Systems (GIS); Chamba-Kangra Districts.*

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Impact of Climate Change on Global Food Security

Chayan Sardar^{1*}, Basira Habiba Belali¹, Samya Sen¹ and Harekrishna Jana²

¹*Techno India University, Department of Microbiology, Salt Lake, Kolkata-700091*

²*Department of Microbiology, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous),
Midnapore-721102, West Bengal*

**Email: chayansardar2020@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Climate change is a big problem for food systems all over the world. It influences the availability, access, use, and stability of food. Agriculture is affected by rising temperatures and severe weather events. Climate change is making global food security less stable by messing up agricultural production, food supply chains, and the quality of food. Higher temperatures, changes in rainfall patterns, and more extreme weather events like floods and droughts make crops and livestock less productive. The Inter-governmental Panel on Climate Change says that climate-related stresses have already hurt the production of staple crops in areas that are already weak. The Food and Agriculture Organization also says that changes in the weather make food prices less stable, which raises the risk of hunger and malnutrition, especially in developing countries. Rise in the average temperature around the world, Rainfall patterns that are not regular, Droughts and floods happen a lot. Heatwaves that hurt crop growth More outbreaks of pests and diseases. Higher levels of carbon dioxide in the air could also lower the protein and micronutrient content of important crops like rice and wheat, making hidden hunger worse. To deal with these problems, we need to use a combination of mitigation and adaptation strategies. These include climate-resilient crop varieties, sustainable farming methods, better irrigation systems, and policy changes that follow international guidelines. Areas that are vulnerable are such as Sub-Saharan Africa, In South Asia and Small Island countries and areas where agricultural systems that rely on rainfall. Climate change poses a direct threat to worlds food security. There is an urgent need for climate-smart farming. For food systems to last, people all over the world need to work together.

Keywords: *Climate; Irrigation systems; Sustainable farming methods; Climate-smart farming.*

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**Investigation of NLO properties of 2-mercapto benzothiazole and its derivatives in
different solvents: A computational approach**

Ranjit Pal and Hasibul Beg*

Department of Chemistry

Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College Autonomous, Midnapore, West Bengal. 721102.

**Email: palranjit@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

The systemic investigation of the electronic structures, non linear optical characteristics, global reactivity descriptors (GRD) and molecular electrostatic potentials (MEPs) of 2-mercapto benzothiazole and its derivatives have been performed by means of density functional theory (DFT) and time dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) methods at CAM-B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) level in Gaussian 16. Amino(-NH₂), Methoxy(-OMe), Fluorine (-F), and Nitro(-NO₂) groups have been chosen as substituent at various position of 2-MBT in this investigation. Substitution of nitro group substantially decreases the |HOMO-LUMO| energy gap and increases charge transfer abilities as determined by FMO study. Nitro-substituted molecules also have the highest degree of electrophilicity, softness and electron affinity compared to all the other derivatives; thus, demonstrates a significantly greater amount of electronic reactivity. There is an inverse relationship between the energy gap and λ_{\max} values in the UV region. MEP calculation has been introduced to find out charge separation and electrophilic sites in the molecules. 2-MBT derivative with nitro group attached to the 6-position shows the highest degree of frequency dependent NLO properties like average polarizability (α_{av}), first hyperpolarizability (β_0) and β_{HRS} in both the gas and solvent phases e.g. water, DMSO, methanol and chloroform. Therefore, nitro-substituted 2-MBT derivative can be used as promising advanced materials for optoelectronic and photonic applications due to their optimized charge transfer properties and high NLO performance.

Keywords: *2-Mercaptobenzothiazole derivatives; Density Functional Theory (DFT); Time-Dependent DFT (TD-DFT); Nonlinear Optical (NLO) Properties; HOMO-LUMO Energy Gap; Global Reactivity Descriptors (GRD).*

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Assessing the spatio-temporal dynamics of canopy density in a tropical dry deciduous forest dominated landscape using Sentinel-2 dataset and Forest Canopy Density (FCD) model

Tanusree Roy^{1*} and Mansa Dey^{1,2}

¹ *Department of Geo-Informatics, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Bankura University, Bankura, West Bengal, India*

² *Department of Geography, Jadavpur University, Kolkata, West Bengal, India*
Email: tanushreeroy1052003@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Canopy density is a crucial indicator for assessing forest structure, ecological health, and vegetation cover conditions. Monitoring canopy density helps to identify forest gaps, degradation, and regeneration patterns, which are essential for sustainable forest management. The present study analyzes the spatio-temporal dynamics (2015 – 2025) of canopy density in the tropical dry deciduous forest dominated landscape of Panchet Forest Division, Bankura district, West Bengal. The Forest Canopy Density (FCD) model was implemented utilizing Sentinel-2 derived biophysical parameters, including Advanced Vegetation Index (AVI), Bare Soil Index (BSI), and Shadow Index (SI). The change detection analysis was conducted by incorporating FCD model derived canopy density of both 2015 and 2025. The predicted canopy density for 2025 was validated using 120 field-based canopy density observations, yielding substantial accuracy ($R^2 = 0.72$). The results reveal that 591.3 km² (49.31%) of the area experienced no change, while 281.60 km² (23.48%) showed positive change and 326.29 km² (27.21%) exhibited negative change in canopy density during the study period. Very Dense Forest (VDF), Moderately Dense Forest (MDF), and Scrub (SF) categories showed a decline in canopy density, whereas Open Forest (OF) recorded an increase in areal extent. Notable class transitions included OF–MDF (129.94 km²), MDF–VDF (54.83 km²), OF–SF (48.85 km²), and MDF–OF (170.40 km²) between 2015 and 2025. These findings highlight the simultaneous influence of natural processes and anthropogenic interventions leading to both regeneration and degradation within the forest ecosystem. Overall, the study highlights the dynamic nature of canopy density in the Panchet Forest Division and emphasizes the importance of continuous monitoring using geospatial techniques to support informed decision making for conservation and management strategies.

Keywords: *Tropical dry deciduous forest; Canopy density, Sentinel; Spatio-temporal dynamics; Panchet Forest Division.*

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Analyzing Blue Carbon Stock of A Mangrove Wetland Through Integration of Multi-Sensory Remote Sensing Dataset, Machine Learning Algorithm and In-Situ Observations

Mansa Dey^{1,2*} and Debajit Datta¹

¹*Department of Geography, Jadavpur University, Kolkata, West Bengal, India*

²*Department of Geo-Informatics, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Bankura University, Bankura, West Bengal, India*

Email: mansadey007@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The organic carbon (C) sequestered in coastal and marine ecosystems (blue C) has gained substantial recognition as a crucial nature-based solution to mitigate climate change and associated environmental degradations. This study assessed the blue C stock and its spatial variability across different land use/ land cover (LULC) in the Bichitrapur mangrove sanctuary, a mangrove wetland situated on the Bay of Bengal coast. The blue C stock of the studied wetland was estimated through integration of multisensory geospatial datasets, in-situ destructive and non-destructive samplings, allometric equations and machine learning algorithms. Among different blue C components, soil organic C (SOC) was estimate dusing spatial interpolation of point-specific SOC density dataset. Above ground biomass (AGB) was estimated by assimilating machine learning algorithms (ANN: artificial neural network, RF: random forest and SVM: support vector machine) utilizing PALSAR-2 and Pleiades-1A derived parameters and in-situ AGB dataset. The below ground biomass (BGB) was computed using allometric equations based on modelled AGB values. The total blue C stock was quantified by combining these components. Further, the variations of blue C stock across different LULCs were examined through one-way analysis of variance. The spline interpolation ($R^2 = 0.74$) and RF algorithm ($R^2 = 0.85$) proved to be the best fit model for SOC and AGB estimations, respectively. The total blue C stock of the site was estimated as 121545.94 ± 76.97 Mg, which is equivalent to 446073.60 ± 282.48 unit of carbon credit. The dense mangrove category exhibited highest mean blue C density (168.22 ± 0.06 Mg ha⁻¹). The mean blue C densities across most of the LULCs were significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from each other, thereby highlighting the forcing of LULC on C sequestration. This study offers pioneering insights into blue C accounting and supports regional and national carbon inventories, highlighting the importance of mangrove ecosystems for achieving India's net-zero carbon goals.

Keywords: *Blue carbon; Coastal wetland; Carbon credit; Mangroves; Machine learning algorithms*

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From Fields to Fishponds: A Study of Socio-Ecological Vulnerability in Moyna CD Block, West Bengal, India

Subhajit Barman* and Avishek Bhunia

Department of Geography, K.D. College of Commerce and General Studies, Midnapore, Paschim Medinipur, 721101, West Bengal, India.

**Email: subhajitbarman413@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

The rapid and unregulated expansion of fisheries ('VERI') through the illegal conversion of fertile paddy field has emerged as a major ecological and socio-economic concern in the Community Development Block of Moyna, West Bengal. Over the past three decades, cultivable lands have increasingly been transformed into commercial fish ponds in pursuit of immediate economic profit. This unscientific process has resulted in significant environmental degradation and growing ecological vulnerability among the local communities. The present study examines the spatial and socio-ecological impacts of this land-use transformation. The research integrates multiple methodological approaches including Land Use-Land Cover (LULC) change detection using Remote Sensing, GIS, and perception analysis through Focus Group Discussions (FGD) and household surveys. Additionally, an ecological cost-benefit analysis was conducted to evaluate the long-term sustainability of brackish water aquaculture practices in the region. The spatio-temporal analysis of land use and land cover change during 2005–2025 indicates a pronounced shift from traditional agricultural landscapes to aquaculture-dominated land use. Agricultural land experienced the highest loss (89.81%), followed by barren land (62.21%) and vegetated areas (43.25%). In contrast, fisheries exhibited the most significant growth (145.36%), while settlement areas expanded by 94.26%, highlighting increasing anthropogenic pressure and the growing dominance of aquaculture-based economic activities in the region. The findings also reveal that, the unprecedented rate of land conversion deteriorate the soil & water quality and responsible for loss of indigenous species and biodiversity. The study highlights the paradox in which perceived economic benefits from aquaculture are actually generating long-term ecological and livelihood vulnerabilities. By identifying the drivers of land-use change and assessing their environmental and social consequences, the study seeks to provide practical guidance for transforming ecological vulnerability into sustainable community resilience.

Keywords: *VERI; Fishponds; Ecological Vulnerability; Spatio-temporal Analysis; Land Use and Land Cover Change.*

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**Assessing the Impact of Rapid Urban Expansion on Vegetation Cover in Kolkata Using
Satellite Imagery**

Sushobhan Majumdar*

*Department of Geography, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Jambani, Bankura, West
Bengal, India*

**Email: sushobhan91@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Rapid urban expansion significantly alters land use and land cover patterns, often leading to the degradation of urban vegetation. This study assesses the impact of accelerated urban growth on vegetation cover in Kolkata using multi-temporal satellite imagery and geospatial techniques. Landsat data spanning the past three decades were analyzed to quantify changes in vegetation distribution and urban built-up areas. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was employed to evaluate vegetation health and density, while supervised classification methods were used to map land use/land cover transitions. The results indicate a substantial decline in dense vegetation, particularly in peri-urban zones, concurrent with a marked increase in built-up land. Urban sprawl was found to be concentrated along major transportation corridors and newly developed residential and commercial clusters. Statistical analysis reveals a strong inverse relationship between built-up expansion and vegetation cover, highlighting the environmental consequences of unplanned urbanization. The findings underscore the need for sustainable urban planning strategies, including the preservation of green spaces and the integration of ecological considerations into development policies. This research demonstrates the effectiveness of remote sensing and GIS tools in monitoring urban ecological transformations and provides valuable insights for policymakers and urban planners seeking to balance development with environmental sustainability.

Keywords: *Urban expansion; Ecological Transformations; NDVI; Vegetation Health; Vegetation Density*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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Water to Plate: Comprehending A Potential Threat to Human Health

Pradyut Bera and Mrinal Mandal*

Department of Geography, Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University, Purulia-723104, West Bengal

**Email: mrinal-mandal@skbu.ac.in*

ABSTRACT

Diversity in food culture is a unique characteristic of India, which caters to a total of 17.94% fish-product consumers. Fish is enriched with different types of vitamins, fatty acids, omega-3, minerals, etc., and is very fond of non-vegetarian people, especially in Bengal, with a belief that consuming fish can lead to good health. A gradual increase in demand for fish triggers the growth of the aquaculture system at an industry scale by introducing supplements for fast growth rate within a short time as a key technique of the blue revolution. Freshwater aquaculture in coastal Bengal, India, has been a new venture for the economy for the last decade. The produced fish (mainly Indian Major Carps: *C. catla*, *L. rohita*, and *C. mrigala*) were collected (n = 12) purposively from aquaculture ponds, primarily stored and transferred using an ice-box, and finally preserved in a -20 °C refrigerator before analysis in Inductively Coupled Plasma – Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP – OES) following internationally recognized guidelines. The analysis portrayed that the produced fish was contaminated with different toxic heavy metal/loids, e.g., Zn, Cd, As, Pb, etc., among which, some are also identified as carcinogens by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). The concentration of those toxic elements is basically the effect of biomagnification in fish muscle, which was found to be recorded as higher than the maximum permissible limit as suggested by the World Health Organization, and can travel towards the upper trophic level through long-term continuous consumption. The Estimated Daily Intake, followed by Total Hazard Quotient and Target Cancer Risk, inferred that the prolonged consumption of such contaminated fish is of enough risk for human health.

Keywords: *Contaminants; Human health; Health indices; Carcinogen; Hazard quotient.*

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**Spatio-Temporal Analysis and Prediction of Land Use and Land Cover Changes Using
CA–Markov Modelling: A Case Study of Purulia Municipality**

Anirban Hatial* and Anup Kumbhakar

*Department of Geography, Manbhum Mahavidyalaya, Manbazar, Purulia, West Bengal-721131
Watershed & Soil Conservation, Barmer Zilla Parishad, Rajasthan-344001*

**Email: hatial.anirban@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) dynamics are crucial for understanding environmental change, urban expansion, and sustainable resource management. This study examines the spatio-temporal changes in LULC within Purulia Municipality, West Bengal, over a 25-year period (2000, 2015, and projected 2026) using advanced geospatial and remote sensing techniques. Five major LULC classes were identified: built-up area, vegetation, water bodies, agricultural land, and barren land.

Change detection analysis between 2000 and 2015 indicates a substantial increase in built-up areas, primarily driven by rapid urbanisation and infrastructure development, accompanied by a decline in agricultural land and vegetation cover. These changes reflect growing anthropogenic pressure on natural land resources. To project future land-use patterns, a Cellular Automata–Markov Chain (CA–Markov) model was employed to simulate LULC conditions for 2026. Model validation using kappa statistics and transition probability matrices demonstrated satisfactory predictive accuracy. The projected scenario for 2026 indicates that cities will continue to grow, vegetative and agricultural areas will remain smaller, and that land will become increasingly fragmented. This will make it much harder to plan for sustainable cities.

The findings highlight the need to integrate geospatial modelling with municipal planning strategies to mitigate environmental degradation and foster evidence-based decision-making. This study provides a scientific baseline for policymakers and planners to formulate effective land management, ecological conservation, and sustainable urban development strategies in Purulia municipality.

Key words: *Land Use and Land Cover (LULC); Urban Expansion; CA–Markov Modelling; Change Detection; Sustainable Urban Planning.*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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**Strengthening Climate Adaptation through Natural Resource Inventory in the
Traditional Farming Areas of the Eastern Ghats Highlands**

Partha Pratim Adhikary*

ICAR – National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use Planning, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India

**Email: ppadhikary@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

The Eastern Ghats highlands of India represent a fragile agro-ecological region where agriculture and rural livelihoods are increasingly threatened by climate change. Rising temperatures, erratic rainfall, soil degradation, declining water resources, and biodiversity loss are significantly affecting farm productivity and sustainability in the region. Over the past five decades, the region has experienced an average temperature increase of about 1.2 °C, declining and irregular rainfall patterns, and increasing frequency of extreme weather events, resulting in crop yield reductions, soil erosion, and water scarcity. Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) offers an integrated pathway to address these challenges by simultaneously enhancing agricultural productivity, strengthening climate resilience, and contributing to climate change mitigation. This work reviews the major climate challenges in the Eastern Ghats and highlights a range of CSA practices suitable for the region. Key practices discussed include conservation agriculture, mulching, zero tillage, crop diversification, agroforestry systems, efficient water management techniques such as rainwater harvesting and drip irrigation, climate-resilient crop varieties, and integrated pest and nutrient management. In addition, community-based approaches such as farmer field schools, participatory decision-making, and the integration of indigenous knowledge are emphasized as essential for successful CSA implementation. These practices have demonstrated multiple benefits, including improved soil health, enhanced water-use efficiency, reduced soil erosion, increased crop productivity, carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, and improved farmer livelihoods. Despite its potential, the adoption of CSA in the Eastern Ghats faces several challenges, including limited farmer awareness, financial constraints, fragmented landholdings, and weak institutional support. The work therefore outlines strategic recommendations such as policy incentives, strengthened research and development, effective technology dissemination, and collaborative stakeholder networks to accelerate CSA adoption. Overall, the integration of climate-smart practices with local knowledge systems and strong institutional support can significantly enhance the resilience and sustainability of farming systems in the Eastern Ghats highlands while improving the socio-economic well-being of smallholder and tribal communities.

Key words: *Climate Resilience; Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA); Eastern Ghats Highlands; Sustainable Farming; Soil and Water Conservation.*

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Human-elephant conflict in Jangalmahal, West Bengal: A rising concern

Dibyendu Das*

*Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Gope Palace, Midnapore, Paschim
Medinipur, West Bengal, 721102*

**E-mail: dibyendudas148@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

South-Bengal (SB) has been witnessing human-wildlife conflict especially human-elephant conflict (HEC) for many years. There are numerous instances of HEC in SB, such as death/injuries of elephants due to attack by mob, electrocution, road accident, train collision and also the death/injuries of human as a result of elephant attack, destruction of crop field and storage, damage of properties and many more. The area of western parts of the SB, often referred to as the Jangalmahal which includes Jhargram, Midnapore, Bankura, Birbhum and Purulia is considered as major hotspots of HEC. The topography, climate, vegetation and hydrology of these areas in relation to the expansion and establishment of new elephant corridors by themselves in past decades impose difficulties in managing HEC. The Wildlife Institute of India reported a remarkable dip (25%) in total elephant population in India in last eight years; the declination is more alarming (84%, in 2017-2023) in SB. Various anthropogenic activities including destruction and fragmentation of natural habitats, unsustainable agriculture, livestock grazing in forest and poaching/trafficking of elephants are major underlying causes of HEC. Considering the facts, several strategies including sustainable agricultural practices, afforestation, habitat restoration, development of elephant feeding areas, educating the tribal/local communities, adoption of elephants, tracking of elephant movements using advanced tools/techniques and proper law enforcement should be implemented as a part of long-term solutions to minimize HEC in SB. The present approach highlights the current scenario and underlying causes of HEC and the possible sustainable solutions for the management of HEC in SB.

Key words: *Human-elephant conflict; Sustainable agriculture; Habitat fragmentation; Habitat restoration; Sustainable approach.*

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**Trend Analysis of Land Area Reduction in Ghoramara Island, Sundarban Using SMA
and EMA**

K. Mondal*, A. K. Lal and D. P. Goswami

Department of Mathematics, PRMS Mahavidyalaya, Bankura, West Bengal

Department of Mathematics, Simdega College, Simdega, Jharkhand

Research fellow, Asutosh Mookerjee memorial institute, Sivatosh Mookerjee Science Centre, Kolkata

** Email ID: kartickmathbhu@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

This paper studies how Ghoramara Island, located in the Hooghly estuary of the Bay of Bengal, India, has been shrinking over time due to global warming and climate change. The island, once about 18.54 square kilometers in 1954, has now reduced to only 2.71 square kilometers because of coastal erosion, sea-level rise and other environmental pressures. The goal of this research is to analyze the trend of this areal reduction using two mathematical tools: the Simple Moving Average (SMA) and the Exponential Moving Average (EMA). The data used in this study include the yearly area of the island from 1970 to the present. The SMA and EMA methods were applied to remove random fluctuations and to reveal the overall trend of shrinkage. The SMA helps to understand the long-term pattern of area reduction by averaging data over several years, while the EMA gives more importance to recent years, showing how quickly the erosion is increasing in the present time. Both SMA and EMA effectively capture the trend of island's shrinking area—SMA showing long-term trends and EMA revealing recent rapid losses. These findings help policymakers plan conservation and relocation strategies, demonstrating how moving averages can be applied to study ecological changes. In conclusion, this research confirms that Ghoramara Island is rapidly disappearing and immediate actions are needed to counter the effects of climate change. The methodology provides a simple yet powerful method to analyze such environmental degradation. This approach can also be used for similar studies of other vulnerable coastal regions in the future.

Keyword: *Ghoramara, Climate Change; Moving Averag; Area Reduction Global Warming; Ecology; Erosion.*

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**Study on the sustainability of edible oyster with climate change through decadal
variation of aquatic p^H and anthropogenic pressure in and around the Indian
Sundarbans**

Harekrishna Jana*

*Dept. of Microbiology (UG&PG), Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College, Paschim Midnapur,
Pin-721152, West Bengal
Email: hkjmicro@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Growth and reproduction of oyster is directed by the pH and salinity of the water. The species reproduce successfully in waters where the pH ranges from 6.0 - 9.0. Oysters requires a minimum of 10 ppt (parts per trillion) salinity level in order to grow at normal rates, with stunting or non-existent growth below 7.5 ppt. Repeat hydrographic and time series data for 30 years in the western Indian Sundarbans exhibit direct evidence for acidification of estuarine water. The long-term trend in surface water pH is interpreted as signal of climate change. Thus conservation of coastal vegetation and mangrove afforestation must be given priority to prevent the rapid fall of pH, which otherwise may pose deleterious effects on the molluscan community of the Sundarban estuary and subsequently lead to an ecological imbalance. Long-time study highlight that the microbial load and heavy metals significantly spatial variations was observed in all the three station (Namkhana, Frazergaunge and Sajnekhali) which can be related to the type and magnitude of anthropogenic activities operating in and around the selected stations. The distribution of heavy metal in water followed the order Zn>Cu>Pb in all the three sampling stations and exhibited a unique seasonal pattern with highest values during monsoon and lowest during pre-monsoon. A long term monitoring is required to understand the spatio-temporal variations of hydrological parameters to sustain the oyster culture which is an alternative livelihood option of coastal people.

Key Word: *Oyster; Indian Sundarbans; heavy metals; Salinity.*

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**Herbal Nutritional Modulation in Koi Carp: Growth and Hemato-immunological
Effects of Palash Flower through dietary addition**

Jayita Gain* and Joydev Maity

Department of Fishery Sciences, Vidyasagar University, Midnapore-721102, West Bengal, India

**Email: gainjayita@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Herbal feed additives have gained increasing attention in aquaculture due to their potential to enhance growth performance and stimulate immune responses. The flowers of *Butea monosperma* (Palash), commonly known as the “Flame of the Forest”, have long been utilized in traditional medicinal systems, particularly in Ayurveda, for their therapeutic properties. This study evaluated the effects of dietary addition with palash flower powder on the growth performance, feed utilization, survival rate, and hemato-immunological parameters of ornamental koi carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L.). A 60-day feeding trial was conducted using five experimental groups (T1–T5), each comprising ten fish reared in separate tanks. The control group (T1) received a basal diet, while treatment groups T2, T3, T4, and T5 were fed diets addition with 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10% palash flower powder, respectively. Fish were fed daily at 4% of their body weight. Among the treatments, T4 (7.5%) demonstrated significantly superior growth performance compared to other groups. Hematological parameters were significantly elevated ($p < 0.05$) in all supplemented groups relative to the control. Serum biochemical indices remained within normal physiological ranges across treatments. Additionally, total immunoglobulin levels were significantly higher in fish receiving palash supplemented diets. The findings indicate that incorporation of 7.5% *Butea monosperma* flower powder in the diet effectively enhances growth, survival, and immune responses in koi carp, suggesting its potential as a natural feed additive in ornamental aquaculture.

Keywords: *Koi carp; Palash flower; Hemato-immunology; Growth; Herbal additives.*

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Spatio-temporal Assessment of Forest Above-Ground Biomass (AGB) and Carbon Stock Dynamics in Jhargram District using Sentinel-2 and Machine Learning

Sambhunath Roy* and Sukha Ranjan Samadder

Department of Environmental Science & Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology (Indian School of Mines), Dhanbad-826004, India.

PG Department of Geography, Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore, West Bengal, India.

** Email: sambhuroynath95@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Estimation of forest Above-Ground Biomass (AGB) are required to be understand the dynamics of terrestrial carbon status and to inform climate mitigation policies. Since, in a fragmented tropical dry deciduous forest, spatio-temporal variation of biomass has not adequately been studied in regional scale. The dynamic of forest AGB and carbon stock is studied in lateritic “Junglemahal” area of Jhargram District. High resolution multispectral images from Sentinel-2 used to compute red-edge vegetation indices and Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) that represent multi-layer canopy structure and heterogeneity of vegetation. Field-based dendrometric attributes such as diameter at breast height (DBH) and tree height, are collected for computation of forest biomass and combined with satellite-based predictors to model spatial biomass distribution using the Random Forest approach. The finding showcasing a strong variability in AGB in the district, relatively higher biomass ($>230 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1}$) was found in the contiguous Sal (*Shorea Robusta*) dominating forest and lower in the fragmented forest areas due to anthropogenic activities. Temporal analysis reveals notable changes in biomass density due to climatic variability and local pressures such as fuelwood harvesting and forest fragmentation. The model developed a good predictive power ($R^2 \approx 0.85$), indicating that the integration of red-edge spectral information, texture features, and machine learning to remotely estimate biomass is possible. The biomass and carbon stock maps produced in this study offer a scalable and cost-efficient tool for assessing forest carbon dynamics and for identifying areas for restoration, which could be used to enhance sustainable forest management as well as climate mitigation in eastern India.

Keywords: *Above-Ground Biomass; Junglemahal, Shorea robusta; Random Forest; Red-edge; Forest Fragmentation; Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix.*

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Role of Yogic Interventions in Regulating Human Physiology

Madhumita Pandey^{1*}, Mousumi Chakraborty¹, Sudeep Mitra², Mousumi Mitra¹, Purna Nandi³,
Md Raihan Uddi¹ and Dilip Kumar Nandi⁴

¹*Department of Human Physiology, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous)*

²*Department of Biological Sciences, Midnapore City College³*

³*Department of BMLT Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous)*

⁴*Department of Food Science and Nutrition, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous)*

**Email: madhumitapandey1977@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Yoga is an ancient Indian disciplines that intrigates physical, mental and spiritual practice to achieve harmony between body and mind. Modern life style characterised by chronic stress lead to autonomic dysregulation, which is precursor to cardiovascular disease, metabolic syndrome and mental health. The present study aimed to evaluate the role of yogic interventions in regulating human physiology by assessing their effects on selected biochemical and physiological parameters related to stress, oxidative balance, and metabolic health. The study was conducted among female college students in a selected college campus in West Bengal, India. The participants were healthy volunteers within the age group of 18–25 years who were experiencing moderate academic and lifestyle-related stress. A total of 450 female college students were selected using a purposive sampling method. The participants underwent a structured yoga intervention program for a period of six months. Physiological and biochemical parameters such as oxidative stress markers (Superoxide Dismutase and Catalase) and lipid profile (total cholesterol, LDL, HDL, and triglycerides) were assessed before and after the intervention. The results indicated a significant improvement in antioxidant enzyme activity, with increased levels of Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) and Catalase after the yoga intervention. A favourable modulation of lipid profile was also observed, including a reduction in total cholesterol, LDL, and triglycerides, along with a mild increase in HDL levels. The study concludes that yogic interventions play an important role in regulating human physiology by enhancing antioxidant defense, improving lipid metabolism, and reducing stress-related physiological disturbances.

Keywords: *Yogic Intervention; Oxidative Stress; Superoxide Dismutase (SOD); Catalase; Lipid Profile.*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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Cyclone-induced causes and effects of the flood in the coastal area of Bangladesh

Md Hasanuzzaman* and Deepak Kumar Mandal

Research Scholar, Department of Geography and Applied Geography, University of North Bengal

I Professor, Department of Geography and Applied Geography, University of North Bengal

**Email: drhasan61@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Bangladesh faces both natural and human-induced disasters with increasing frequency and intensity, making it one of the most disaster-prone countries in the world. This study examines cyclone-induced coastal flooding and its associated impacts in the southern districts of Bangladesh. Floods are among the most common natural hazards affecting the coastal region, causing widespread damage to agriculture, shrimp aquaculture, transportation networks, infrastructure, settlements, and other forms of property. Approximately three crore people live in low-lying coastal zones and are highly vulnerable to extreme climatic events such as tidal surges, monsoon storms, cyclones, and saline water inundation. The major tidal zones include Khulna–Patuakhali, Noakhali–Bhola–Shariatpur, and Chittagong–Cox’s Bazar regions, where the elevation is generally less than three metres above mean sea level. As a result, every year, natural disasters lead to severe infrastructure loss, environmental degradation, and human casualties. Cyclones in the Bay of Bengal typically occur twice a year, during April–May and October–November, intensifying the risk of coastal flooding. This study employs a comprehensive methodology involving literature review, hypothesis development, and primary data collection. Primary data were gathered through focus group discussions, key informant interviews, direct field observation, and mapping of location-based information. Secondary data were collected from the Bangladesh Meteorological Department, Hydrology offices, government reports, and relevant scientific journals. The findings aim to support evidence-based policy decisions, enhance flood preparedness, and contribute to sustainable coastal resource management. The study further provides guidance for developing effective recovery strategies and disaster preparedness plans for coastal communities.

Keywords: *Cyclone-induced flood; Coastal zone; Disaster vulnerability; Storm surge; Tidal inundation; Climate change; Seasonal flooding.*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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Spatio-Temporal Variations in River Morphology: A Study of Selected Reaches of the Ganga Basin

Papri Ray* and Arnab Kundu

Department of Geo-Informatics, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Bankura University, Bankura, West Bengal, India

**Email: raypapri166@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

River dynamics involve a complex interaction of flowing water, sediment movement, and ongoing changes in landforms, all of which significantly shape the surrounding landscape and affect both communities and natural ecosystems. This study examines how the Ganga River system changes over space and time, focusing on three key stretches: the central Uttar Pradesh segment from Fatehpur to Prayagraj, the middle Ganga valley in Varanasi (including Chiraiya and Kashi Vidyapeeth), and the lower Bhagirathi-Hooghly corridor in West Bengal. Using the wide spatial reach and consistent time-based data provided by Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), the research tracks patterns of river meandering and structural changes along the middle and lower sections of the Ganga. Multi-spectral satellite imagery is used to measure physical transformations, while the Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI) helps accurately extract and map water bodies. The Sinuosity Index and Braid Index are applied to evaluate the extent of river meandering and channel complexity, and cross-sections generated from Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) offer detailed insights into slope variations and channel form. An important part of the research involves examining Erosion and Accretion to identify areas where land is being worn away or built up through sediment deposition, helping to better understand the river's hydrological framework. Overall, the findings provide a detailed picture of how the river behaves and evolves, supplying essential information for flood management, water resource planning, and maintaining ecological balance. By studying these changes, the research supports more effective river management and soil conservation efforts in one of the world's most densely populated river basins, where such environmental shifts directly impact local communities.

Keywords: *River Dynamics, Erosion and Accretion, Channel Morphology, Geospatial Technology, Ganga River Basin.*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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Rabindranath's Environmental Thought: A New Study

Mrinalkanti Murmu*

Research Scholar, Department of Bengali, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous)
**Email: mrinalkantimurmu3@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Rabindranath Tagore is one of the brightest personalities of the Bengali literary world. He was a poet, novelist, dramatist, short story writer, essayist, musician, composer, painter, actor and singer—above all a unique and versatile genius. With his multifaceted talents, he moved freely across different branches of literature and left remarkable contributions in each field. Therefore, it is difficult to identify Tagore's excellence within any single domain; he was an accomplished artist in every respect and a profound thinker. As a universal poet, a poet of nature and humanism, he gave new dimensions to the experiences of life and the world through his creations.

The establishment of Visva-Bharati at Santiniketan in a natural environment reflects Tagore's positive vision toward nature and the environment. It symbolizes a meeting place of the world within India and expresses the poet's deep sense of the cosmic spirit. In this context, the testimony of the poet himself is significant-

"I am the poet of the world, wherever he rises, his voice rises
He will wake up to the sound of my flute."

Tagore found the materials of his creative expression in the diversity of nature. Various elements of the physical environment—soil, water, air, sky and natural surroundings—appear in his works with renewed meaning. His writings reveal deep compassion for human life and an intimate relationship between humanity and nature. From his childhood experiences with nature, later travels to the Himalayas, and his stay in rural Bengal at Shilaidaha, nature continuously inspired his imagination. Works like *Jeevansmriti*, *Chinnapatra*, and several short stories such as *Balai*, *Subha*, and *Samapti* vividly portray nature as a living presence.

Tagore's environmental consciousness was also reflected in his initiatives at Santiniketan and Sriniketan. His vision emphasized harmony between humans and nature. In Rabindra literature, three main elements can be observed—Man, Nature and Brahman. Among them, nature occupies a central place, making Tagore both a poet of nature and a poet of humanity.

Keywords: *Environmentalism; Anturghar; Nature depiction; Rabindra's vision.*

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Environmental Conservation in the Uddhava Gita: A Study

Somnath Chakraborty*

Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore, West Bengal- 721102

Email: somnathchakraborty2022@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In our society, the mention of the “Gita” immediately brings the *Srimad Bhagavad Gita* to mind. However, apart from the Bhagavad Gita, there are nearly sixty-four other Gitas, among which the *Uddhava Gita* is particularly significant. In this text, Lord Krishna imparts profound spiritual teachings to Uddhava along with a meaningful perspective on the conservation of nature and the environment. The teachings derived from the twenty-four Gurus of the Avadhuta (wandering ascetic) are especially important and remain relevant even in the context of modern environmental thought.

One of the most essential elements of the environment is the tree. The *Uddhava Gita* teaches that trees should be regarded as a Guru. A tree tolerates scorching sun, storms, and rain while offering shelter to others. Even when it is cut down, it continues to give shade and benefit others. This teaches human beings the virtue of patience and the duty to protect nature rather than destroy it. The Gita also instructs us to learn from the mountain. Trees, grass, and plants grow on mountains, and rivers and springs flow from them, all existing for the welfare of others. The mountain itself does not consume anything for its own benefit. By accepting the mountain as a teacher, one should dedicate life to the welfare of others and understand that human birth is meant for the common good. Such realization helps in protecting the environment.

The Earth is regarded as our mother who nurtures life despite constant exploitation and injustice. Even when trampled or harmed, the Earth remains firm in her position. From the Earth we learn patience, tolerance, and steadfastness. Respecting the Earth and stopping its abuse is the first step toward environmental conservation. Water, the essence of life, teaches purity and transparency. Just as water purifies everything, a wise person should remain pure and clear. Similarly, air carries fragrance and foul odor without attachment, reminding us to live in nature without polluting it. Finally, the *Uddhava Gita* teaches that all elements of nature—sky, air, fire, water, earth, sun, moon, stars, trees, rivers, and oceans—are manifestations of the Divine. Recognizing this truth encourages environmental protection. Thus, the *Uddhava Gita* teaches that protecting nature is an essential part of human life, for if we protect nature, nature will protect us.

Keywords: *Lessons learned from trees; Lessons learned from the earth; Lessons learned from the air; Lessons learned from water; Seeing God in all beings.*

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Machine Learning based sustainable inventory management model in fuzzy environment

Tannistha Das Dhara, Ajoy Kumar Maiti and Suman Maity*

*Department of Mathematic, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous),
Midnapore-721101, India*

**Email:ajoy_maiti2003@yahoo.co.in*

ABSTRACT

This is the era of transition from Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0 where Industry 5.0 leads to the sustainable inventory management that integrate economic objectives with environmental considerations such as carbon emissions, energy consumption, waste reduction , recycling etc. The aim of the study is to formulate single/multi-objective EOQ/EPQ type optimization problems integrating carbon emission reduction, waste minimization, preservation investment and ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) considerations under uncertain environments. Machine learning methods and artificial intelligent techniques have been used to address the demand forecasting that leads to minimize lead time maintaining sustainability objectives. Advanced optimization techniques like fuzzy goal programming, genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization, and classical gradient-based methods etc. has been employed to derive optimal decision variables. Sensitivity analysis has been performed to managerial insights into the impact of ESG uncertainty and regulatory changes on inventory decisions.

Keywords: *Sustainable Inventory Management; Multi-Objective Optimization; Uncertain Environment; Carbon Emission Reduction; Machine Learning; Artificial Intelligence.*

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**Quorum Sensing and Environmental Modulation of *Vibrio cholerae*: A
Rising Epidemiological Concern in India**

Prithwiraj Mukherjee*

*Department of Physiology, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous),
Midnapore-721102, India*

**Email: prithwisir@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Cholera has been categorized as one of the “emerging and re-emerging infections” threatening in India. Seven distinct pandemics of cholera have occurred since the onset of the first recorded pandemic in 1817. Most of the pandemics originated from the Ganges delta and spread to other countries, affecting many regions and extending over many years. The fifth and sixth pandemics were caused by *Vibrio cholerae* classical biotype, whereas the seventh pandemic was caused by *Vibrio cholerae* El Tor biotype. In October 1992, a novel strain named *Vibrio cholerae* MO10 cal phi emerged as the main cause of cholera in Calcutta, India, with some unique genetic features that were not found in previous outbreaks. These facts have led scientists to understand the environmental events that are crucial for triggering the evolution of future epidemic clones. This organism enhances its survival potential in the aquatic environment by expressing exopolysaccharide (EPS) matrix molecules and by forming biofilm. In a previous study, we found that the absence of flagellum can lead to enhanced EPS expression. In another study, it was established that EPS is regulated in a cell density-dependent manner, popularly known as quorum sensing. In view of this, we are targeting genes responsible for quorum sensing and well-known flagellum-mediated signal transduction for the expression of EPS as well as virulence factors by this organism. We conducted deletion mutations and generated single or double mutant strains and tested their phenotypic expression in terms of EPS and biofilm formation and virulence factor expression. Results reveal that quorum sensing autoinducer has a predominant role in the regulation of EPS expression over flagellum-deficient conditions, although they have a complex relationship in the internal signalling cascade. Therefore, quorum sensing autoinducer may be targeted for further research to combat cholera in the future.

Keywords: *Quorum Sensing; Biofilm; Vibrio cholera; Autoinducer.*

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**Sustainable way of MSW Management through Resource Recovery from Municipal
Dumping Site: A case study on Midnapore Municipality**

Subrata Patra*, Partha Pratim Chakravorty and Rupa Dasgupta

Research Scholar, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore-721102, India.

Debra Thana Sahid Kshudiram Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Debra, West Bengal, India

Email: spatra24.geo@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Rapid urbanization and improvement of the living quality have led to a tremendous growth in Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) generation, with approximately 2.01 billion tonnes produced globally per year. Among the total generated waste around 40% wastes are mismanaged, particularly in developing countries over 80% of waste is often disposed of by open dumping (popularly known as dumping ground). India has more than 3100 operational dumpsites across the country. Only 25-30% MSW are treated remaining are disposed in dumpsite without treatment. This condition create significant environmental (methane emissions, soil/water pollution) and public health risks. In India legacy waste dumpsites containing an estimated around 250 million metric tonnes of accumulated, untreated wastes. Midnapore municipality is a class-I census town of the West Bengal. Around 90tonnes of MSW generated per day and disposed at Dharma dump site without any treatment.

Effective MSW management emphasizes a hierarch where reduction, recycling and recover are prioritized. Resource recovery of MSW transforms waste into valuable materials and energy through recycling, composting, and thermal/biological processes. Legacy wastes are the potential source for recovery through landfill mining and biomining. In Midnapore municipality Dharma dumping ground is only operational dump site, it using around 50 years. This site receives waste with a composition of 60-65% organic, 10- 12% plastics, and remaining are glass, cloths, and inert material. This disposed state that legacy waste of the dharma dump site is potential for resource recovery. This review assesses the potentiality of resource recovery and economic viability of the Dharma dump site.

Keywords: MSW; Resource recovery; Legacy waste; Waste Management; Circular Economy.

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**Hidden Impacts of Coal Mining on Groundwater Systems: Hydrogeochemical Evidence
from the Jharia Coalfield**

Amit Bera*, Rohit Banerjee, Rajwardhan Kumar and Sanjit Kumar Pal

*Department of Applied Geophysics, Indian Institute of Technology (Indian School of
Mines) Dhanbad, Dhanbad-826004, Jharkhand, India*

**Email: amitbera12312@yahoo.com*

ABSTRACT

Groundwater resources in coal-mining regions are highly vulnerable to contamination from intensive mining activities, industrial discharges, and other anthropogenic pressures. This study evaluates aquifer contamination and groundwater quality in the Jharia Coalfield, located in Dhanbad, eastern India, using an integrated hydrogeochemical and spatial analysis approach. Groundwater samples from shallow aquifers were analysed for key physicochemical parameters (pH, TDS, EC, and TH) and major ions including Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , HCO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , Cl^- , NO_3^- , and F^- . The results reveal significant spatial variability in groundwater chemistry, reflecting the combined influence of natural geochemical processes and mining-related disturbances. Calcium (22–168.9 mg/L) and magnesium (12.3–85 mg/L) indicate carbonate and silicate weathering, while elevated sodium (5.14–255.5 mg/L) suggests ion exchange and anthropogenic inputs. Sulphate (10.9–148.06 mg/L) reflects sulphide mineral oxidation and mine drainage, whereas nitrate shows high variability (1.1–364.9 mg/L), indicating agricultural runoff and sewage infiltration. Seasonal groundwater levels range from 1.90–11.0 m below ground level during the pre-monsoon and 1.0–6.0 m during the post-monsoon, reflecting recharge controlled by rainfall, lithology, and topography. Water Quality Index (WQI) analysis indicates that several mining-dominated zones fall into the unsuitable for drinking category (WQI > 100), while large parts of the region exhibit very poor water quality. Groundwater quality is relatively better in the limited northern and central areas. The results highlight the growing impacts of both geogenic processes associated with Gondwana sediments and anthropogenic contamination from mining activities, emphasising the need for continuous aquifer monitoring and sustainable groundwater management in coal-mining regions.

Keywords: *Hydrogeochemistry; Groundwater contamination; Coal mining impacts; Water Quality Index; Jharia Coalfield.*

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**Documentation of Indigenous Cosmetic Ethnomedicinal Practices and their
Implications for Medicinal Plant Conservation in Tribal Region of Chota Nagpur
Plateau**

Ishika Gantait* and Nilanjana Das Chatterjee

Department of Geography, Vidyasagar University, Midnapore, West Bengal-721102, India

**Email: ishikagantait6@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

In global scenario the demand of traditional herbal cosmetic knowledge is increasing day by day. It has very strong potentiality not only in growing herbal industries but also in economic development. Generally the ethnomedicinal importance of this species makes them very valuable in both culturally and economically but the investigation and documentation on cosmetic purpose and its implication on resource conservation remain unexplored. The study was conducted in the eastern plateau tribal region of Chota Nagpur plateau, which extended across Jharkhand (Musabani block) and Western West Bengal (Binpur II and Jambani block of Jhargram district). An ethnobotanical survey was conducted on 350 tribal household with a semi structure questionnaire during 2024-2026. Several quantitative indices were employed to understand the use and importance, knowledge insight and conservation attitude. A total 48 cosmetic recipes have been recorded. All the recipes are cross – verified with several available pharmacognostic literature. The conservation attitude are analysed with several multivariate modelling. Promoting sustainable use and its preservation is the main way to conserve the knowledge and preserve the cultural economic benefits.

Keywords: *Traditional herbal cosmetic; Ethnomedicine; Resource conservation; Phytochemical.*

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**In Vitro Assessment of Antimicrobial and Enzymatic Activities of Seed-Borne
Endophytic Fungi from *Cuminum cyminum* L.**

Shusrita Debnath^{1*}, Rashmi Mukherjee¹ and Mrinal Kanti Paira²

¹Dept. of Botany, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore-721102

²Dept. of Chemistry, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore-721102

*Email: debnathshusrita93@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Cumin (*Cuminum cyminum* L.), a member of the Apiaceae family, is highly valued for its culinary versatility and its therapeutic efficacy in treating gastrointestinal ailments such as dysentery, vomiting, diarrhea, and flatulence. While this resilient species thrives in cold, dry climates, it also serves as a host for mycoendophytes. These endophytic fungi proliferate within the plant tissues, offering various biological benefits in exchange for nutrients and shelter. This study aimed to isolate and identify the fungal endophyte population residing within the seeds of *C. cyminum* L. and to evaluate their antibacterial and extracellular enzymatic potential. Fungal strains were isolated from cumin seeds and purified using Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) media. Identification was conducted through a combination of macromorphological and microscopical characterization, followed by molecular analysis using PCR and BLAST sequencing. Six distinct endophytic fungal species were identified, the majority of which belonged to the subdivision Ascomycotina: *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Aspergillus sp.* and one unidentified fungal structure. Among the isolates, *Aspergillus fumigatus* emerged as the most bioactive strain. It demonstrated superior antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*, MTCC87, *Bacillus subtilis*, MTCC121) and Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*, MTCC119, *Salmonella typhi*, MTCC98) bacteria. Furthermore, *A. fumigatus* exhibited the highest extracellular enzymatic levels for amylase, pectinase, and gelatinase, highlighting its potential for biotechnological and pharmaceutical applications.

Keywords: *Cuminum cyminum* L., Mycoendophytes, Antibacterial activity, Extracellular enzyme, *Aspergillus fumigatus*.

Quercetin Supplementation Mitigates Stress-Induced Alterations in Gut Microbiota and Hematological Indices among Female College Students in a Climate Change Context

Mousumi Chakraborty^{1*}, Purna Nandi¹, Mousumi Mitra¹, Mrinal Kanti Paira² and Dilip Kumar Nandi³

¹Department of Human Physiology, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous)

²Department of Chemistry, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous)

³Department of Biological Sciences, Paramedical and Allied Health Sciences, Midnapore City College

*E mail: mousumi1982chakraborty@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Climate change has emerged as a significant global challenge affecting both physical and psychological health. Rising temperatures, environmental instability, and changing lifestyle patterns contribute to increased stress levels among young adults, particularly college-going female students who are already exposed to academic and social pressures. Quercetin, a naturally occurring flavonoid with potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, has gained growing attention for its potential role in modulating gut health and cellular function. The present investigation highlights the multidimensional role of quercetin in modulating gut micro biota and intestinal tissue structure, antioxidant defences, and immune cell response, which are all critical factors in stress regulation of college-going female students who were experiencing stress based on the PGI score scale. Some haematological indices were measured and compared by Chi square test and ANOVA. Stool samples of total 450 no of college students of different age groups were analyzed for total *aerobics*, *Salmonella sp.*, *lactic acid bacteria*, *Bifidobacterium sp.*, and *E. coli* before and after quercetin supplementation. Results indicated a significant reduction in *Salmonella sp.* and *E. coli* counts and *total aerobes*, accompanied by a marked increase in beneficial *lactic acid bacteria* and *Bifidobacterium sp.*, suggesting a positive modulation of gut microbiota. Improved intestinal villi integrity, as evidenced by SEM analysis, supports enhanced nutrient absorption and gut barrier function. The findings indicated that higher stress levels were associated with variations in haematological indices, particularly in immune-related parameters such as WBC and neutrophil counts, suggesting physiological responses to psychological stress. After quercetin supplementation, significant improvements were observed in several haematological parameters across age groups, indicating enhanced immune stability and better physiological adaptation to stress. Overall quercetin supplementation showed a better result for preventing stress through modulating gut brain axis and reducing ROS generation.

Keywords: Stress; Quercetin; Gut-brain axis; Climate change.

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Climate Vulnerability and Gender Marginality: Assessing the Effects of Climate Change on the Lifestyle of Transgender Hijra Communities in the Kolkata Metropolitan Area

Sibsankar Mal*

Department of Geography, Sukumar Sengupta Mahavidyalaya, Keshpur, West Bengal- 721150

**Email: sibsankarmalgeo@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Climate change has emerged as a multidimensional challenge affecting urban populations through rising temperatures, extreme weather events, flooding, and disruptions to livelihoods. However, its impacts are not experienced uniformly across social groups. This research examines how climate change influences the lifestyle, livelihood security, health, and social resilience of transgender Hijra communities in the Kolkata Metropolitan Area. Hijra individuals often occupy socio-economically marginalized positions characterized by limited access to stable employment, housing insecurity, inadequate healthcare, and social exclusion. These vulnerabilities intensify the risks posed by climate-induced hazards such as heat waves, urban flooding, waterlogging, and public health crises. The study explores how environmental stressors intersect with gender identity-based marginalization to shape the everyday experiences of Hijra individuals. Climate-related disruptions may affect informal income sources such as street-based work, community performances, and small-scale informal businesses, thereby destabilizing economic security. In addition, inadequate housing conditions and limited access to safe public infrastructure increase their exposure to extreme weather events. As temperatures continue to rise due to climate change, many members of the transgender community rely on multiple electric fans, air coolers, or air conditioners to cope with heat stress and maintain basic living comfort. Consequently, the growing dependence on cooling devices significantly increases electricity consumption and utility costs. Despite limited financial resources, these additional expenses become unavoidable for survival during extreme heat conditions, indirectly intensifying economic hardship and deepening financial vulnerability within the community. To examine these complex interactions between climate change and gender-based marginalization, this study adopts a mixed-method research design that integrates quantitative survey data with qualitative insights to capture both statistical patterns and lived experiences. The total sample size of the study is 267 Hijra individuals residing across different parts of the Kolkata Metropolitan Area. By highlighting the intersection of environmental change and gender marginality, the study emphasizes the need for inclusive climate adaptation strategies. It argues that climate justice and urban resilience planning must include gender-diverse populations to ensure equitable access to resources, affordable energy, and inclusive support systems.

Keywords: *Climate Change; Extreme Heat; Hijra; Transgender Communities; Social Marginalization; Kolkata Metropolitan Area.*

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A Quest for ‘Transformative Utopias’: Reimagining Select Australian Young Adult and Children’s Fiction

Soumyadeep Chakraborty* and Sudeshna Rana

Department of English, Raja Narendralal Khan Women’s College (Autonomous), Midnapore-721102, India

**Email: sdchakkotti@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Contemporary writings for children and young adults have been highly responsive to global climate change issues. Australian young adult and children’s fiction, with a strong focus on the habitat, flora and fauna of Indigenous and non-Indigenous Australia and its islands, is significantly coming up to address these issues. Critical of imperialism, Victor Kelleher’s novel *Red Heart* (2001) presents the struggle and fall of Young Nat in apocalyptic Australia after an event called Greenhouse has left the once drought-stricken continent facing massive flood and disease. Frances Bodkin’s *D’harawal Seasons and Climatic Cycles* (2008) brings to the fore the gradual effacement of the true essence of Indigenous Australia and marks the damaging weather and climate fluctuations. John Coetzee’s *Dance of the Freaky Green Gold* (2008) offers avenues to fight environmental degradation and climate change through the development of alternative biofuels. Set in the post-sea-level-rising phenomena in Sydney, Alison Stewart’s young adult dystopian fiction *Days Like This* (2011) evokes great concerns for the diminishing natural resources and ‘the rise of heartless individuality’. From the critical paradigm of the futuristic reconfigurations of ‘transformative utopias’ in young adult and children’s fiction as theorised by Clare Bradford and Robyn McCallum, my paper seeks to analyse how these texts move beyond the environmental apocalypse and represent an inclusive subjectivity and human-nature relationship. Highlighting the issues of ecological degradation and climate change, my paper also explores how these children’s texts reconsider issues like habitat protection, celebration of ‘Indigenous wilderness’, ecosystem conservation, pollution prevention and resource depletion and look forward to shaping a better world order. Applying Colleen Mack-Canty’s critical parlance of advocating the harmonic balance between nature and culture, the paper also examines how these texts address the preservation of human rights to ensure the future well-being of the human species on the planet by ‘re-weaving’ the culture/nature duality and ‘incorporating embodiment and nonhuman nature’.

Keywords: *Indigenous; Transformative utopias; Culture/nature; Embodiment; Nonhuman nature.*

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Relationship between Economic Growth and Environmental Degradation: A Cross-section Analysis on few Countries

Suman Chakraborty*

*Department of Economics, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous),
Midnapore 721102, W.B, India.*

**Email: sumanchakraborty404@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the relationship between Economic growth and Environmental degradation through multiple regression analysis. Economic growth is measured in terms of per capita real GDP and Environmental degradation is estimated in terms of per capita Carbon-dioxide emissions. Relationship of some other explanatory variables like ICT, dependency ratio, urbanization and renewable energy consumption are also observed with respect to environmental degradation. The entire study is based on secondary data which are collected from World Bank report and other economic survey report. The selected countries categorized as per World-Bank's income criterion (HICs, LICs, LMICs & UMICs).

Keywords: *Economic Growth; Environmental degradation; HICs; LICs; LMICs & UMICs.*

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**Effect of seasonality and agriculture field characters on breeding biology of Red-wattled
lapwing and Yellow-wattled lapwing**

Arnab Shee and Supratim Mukherjee*

Department of Zoology, Government General Degree College, Singur, West Bengal, India

**Email: supratimm7@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Red-wattled lapwing and Yellow-wattled lapwing are non migratory bird and largely occupied to oriental region. RWL extends into parts of the Middle East within the Palaearctic, whereas YWL is restricted to the Indian Subcontinent. Both species are generally ground nesting birds and occupying agricultural and non agricultural landscape. Aims of our study to see how seasonality and agricultural field characters are effects on their breeding biology. Study was carried out in agricultural field of lower Gangetic plain of Hooghly district, West Bengal, India. The effects of predictors on clutch size and brood size were assessed using linear mixed-effects models. Top model suggested that clutch size of RWL was affected by field type, seasonality, vegetation height-and their interactive interaction - seasonality×vegetation height. Model prediction indicated clutch size decreases with seasonality. Clutch size of YWL mostly influenced by cropping phase, seasonality and their interaction. Predicted clutch slightly increased during 1st phase, while moderately and strongly decreased during 2nd and 3rd phase of cropping respectively. Field type independently and its interaction with vegetation height were the strongest to affect brood size. Model predicted brood size to be increased and decreased with increasing vegetation height within stubble field and potato field respectively.

Keywords: *Lapwing; Agriculture field; Field type; Seasonality; Vegetation; Linear mixed-effects models.*

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The Kisan Mandies in Rural Economy: A case Study of Dhaniakhali Block in Hooghly District & Jamalpur Block in East Burdwan of West Bengal.

Papiya Dey and Rajesh Dey*

*Department of Geography, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous),
Midnapore -721102, West Bengal, India
Email: rdey3312@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In late sixties of the 20th century Government of India launched Green Revolution to augment agricultural production and to foster agro market. In tandem of this policy a new concept Kisan Mandi was introduced a network of Mandies with an institutional structure and functions were formed in western part of India particularly in the State of Punjab, Haryana & Maharashtra. The Mandies in general helped the Peasants in modernising agriculture, in extending market opportunities, in getting capital flow & in stabilising agricultural prices. The invention of Mandies accelerated diversification of crops , boosted agro capital & helped industrial development & protected farmers, interests with a scheme of Minimum Support Price of the crops declared from time to time. The flexible credits from the Banks to the farmers on basis of the specific suggestions of the Mandies from time to time, from crops to crops helped the Kisans from shortage of capital flow and thereby stabled production of crops. The scientific knowledge of farming and role of the Mandies in channelizing information & as well as in providing high quality seeds including market options created leverage in rural economy of Punjab, although not free from shortcomings & new types of contradiction. The new Agricultural laws (2020) invited changes & came out to address the problems of the rural economy with new inputs. The concept of Kisan Mandies is relatively new one in West Bengal where agro land ownership is not compatible with Punjab. Here ownership is too fragmented, Irrigation, marketing, modernisation & crediting is lagging far behind from Western part of India.

Keywords: *Kisan Mandi; Stabilising; Minimum Support Price; Flexible credits; Channelizing information and Modernisation.*

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**Finfish Biodiversity and Conservation Strategies with Reference to Socio-economic
Conditions of Fisher-folk in the Subarnarekha River Basin, India**

Mrinmay Ghorai*

*Dept. of Zoology, Panskura banamali College (Autonomous)
Panskura, Purba Medinipur-721152, West Bengal, India
Email: mrghorai@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Riverine ecosystems play a crucial role in supporting freshwater biodiversity and sustaining the livelihood of millions of people in tropical regions. Freshwater fish constitute an important source of protein and income for socio-economically weaker communities. However, freshwater ecosystems are increasingly threatened by anthropogenic pressures such as pollution, habitat modification, overexploitation, and climate change. The present study aims to assess finfish biodiversity, analyse community structure, evaluate ecological integrity, and examine the socio-economic conditions of fisher-folk in the Subarnarekha River basin. The river originates near Nagri village on the Chota Nagpur Plateau and flows the 395 km before entering the Bay of Bengal. For the present investigation, ten sampling stations were selected across the three states, including Galudi, Ghatsila and Jamsola (Jharkhand); Gopiballavpur, Mahapal, Bhasraghat, Dantan Ferrighat and Sonakonia-Mirjapur (West Bengal); and Rajghat and Chowmukh-Talsari (Odisha). Field surveys combined fish sampling, geocoding using GPS, remote sensing support, and physicochemical water quality analysis following standard methods. Collected fish specimens were identified using standard taxonomic keys and fish databases. The study documented about 90 freshwater fish species belonging to 20 orders, 40 families and 63 genera. The order Cypriniformes was found to be the most dominant (33.3%), followed by Siluriformes (16.7%) and Perciformes (12.2%). Several small indigenous fish species such as *Amblypharyngodon mola*, *Puntius sophore*, *Mystus gulio*, *Ompok pabda* and *Cirrhinus reba* were commonly recorded across sampling stations. However, increasing pollution from mining activities, untreated industrial and domestic effluents, and other anthropogenic disturbances have significantly affected the ecological health of the river. Socio-economic assessment revealed that local fisher-folk communities are highly dependent on the river for livelihood and food security. The study emphasizes the need for sustainable fisheries management, habitat restoration, pollution control and community-based conservation strategies to ensure long-term biodiversity conservation and improve the livelihood of riverine fishing communities.

Keywords: *Conservation strategies; Finfish diversity; Fisher-folk livelihood; Freshwater biodiversity; Subarnarekha River.*

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Fisheries and Sustainable Economy: A Study of the Swarupnagar Block in North 24 Parganas

Krishna Kumar Sarkar*

*Department of History, Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Gope Palace,
Paschim Medinipur-721102.*

**Email: krishnakumarsarkar08@gmail.com*

The Swarupnagar area, located in the North 24 Parganas district of West Bengal, holds significant geographical and economic importance. Situated at 22.8333° North and 88.8667° East, this community development block is bordered by Gaighata to the north, Baduria to the south and west, and Habra-I to the northwest, while its eastern boundary meets Kalaroa Upazila of the Satkhira district in Bangladesh. The region lies within the Ichamati–Raymangal plain of the lower Ganga delta and is characterized by fertile alluvial soil ranging from mature black loam to recent silt. The Ichamati River flowing along the eastern boundary serves as a vital lifeline for the local population.

Covering an area of about 215.13 square kilometers, the block is administered by one Panchayat Samiti and ten Gram Panchayats, comprising 66 inhabited villages. These villages support an economy largely dependent on agriculture and fisheries. Due to the low-lying topography, the presence of wetlands, and the network of canals connected with the Ichamati River, the region provides ideal conditions for fish farming. Over time, many agricultural lands have been transformed into 'bheris' or large-scale fish farms. Along with common freshwater species such as Rui and Katla, high-value species like Pabda, Tangra, Chital, and prawns are commercially cultivated. Fish farming in Swarupnagar plays a crucial role in sustaining the rural economy and providing employment to thousands of people. Activities related to feed supply, fish trading, transportation, net making, ice production, and fish packing have developed around this sector. The active participation of local women in net weaving and fish seed selection has also encouraged economic self-reliance and social empowerment. The region demonstrates elements of sustainable aquaculture, where farmers grow bananas, papayas, and vegetables along pond embankments using nutrient-rich water as natural fertilizer. These water bodies also help in rainwater retention and groundwater recharge. However, challenges such as border restrictions, natural disasters, fish diseases, and the influence of middlemen often limit the farmers' profits. With improved scientific management, cold storage facilities, and modern technologies like biofloc, Swarupnagar has the potential to become a strong model of sustainable rural economic development in West Bengal.

Keywords: *Aquaculture; Sustainable Economy; Wetland Management; Rural Livelihoods; and Swarupnagar Block, etc.*

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Geospatial Assessment of Flash Flood Hazard in the Northwestern Himalayas

Sahanaj Parvin Khan* and Arnab Kundu

*Department of Geo-Informatics, Pandit Raghunath Murmu Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Bankura
University, Bankura, West Bengal, India*

**Email: sahanajkhan189@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Flash floods are the fastest and most devastating natural hazards especially in the mountainous areas with high altitude, steep slopes, weak geology and heavy rainfall that cause runoffs to be generated faster. Mountain ranges like the Himalayas, Andes and European Alps are common all over the world and are prone to flash floods caused by heavy rainfall, unexpected thawing of snow and sudden water release in the upstream scenario. Such occurrences usually lead to drastic effects on settlements, infrastructure, agriculture, and ecosystem in downstream mountain valleys. The Himalayan region of India is very prone to flash floods at the national level because of the complex terrain, a monsoon-controlled climate and the high density of rivers passing through the region. Such events are common in the states like Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh and Sikkim. The 2013 Kedarnath Floods and the Teesta River Basin floods show the growing susceptibility of the Himalayan catchments, whereby a sudden increase in runoff, which occurs rapidly in steep valleys, might result in sudden flooding. Climate change has also increased the incidences of flash floods in mountainous areas. Increase in temperature, change in the pattern of precipitation and the frequency of the extreme rain occurrence are major factors affecting the hydrological processes. Increased temperature in the atmosphere increases the ability of moisture to be held leading to short-lived but intense rainfall. Moreover, geomorphological and environmental factors like slope gradient, drainage density, land-use and land-cover alterations, and soil nature are very vital in the formation of flash floods. The current research is on Chamba District and Kangra District situated in the north-western parts of Himalayan region in Himachal Pradesh. The region is marked by rough landscape, steepness and heavy downpour. The region is very prone to flash floods and this is because of the several rivers that originate in the Dhauladhar Range that pass through the region. In this research, geospatial and remote sensing are used to evaluate flash floods. The integration of various datasets such as Sentinel-, Sentinel-, Sentinel-, CHIRPS Rainfall Data and SRTM DEM was done in a GIS environment. It has been analyzed that there exist spatial differences in the intensity of rainfall and runoff controlled by the terrain. The combined geospatial methodology helps to determine a number of the most vulnerable flash-flood areas in Chamba and Kangra, which is informative to conduct the flood risk assessment and disaster management planning in the Himalayan area.

Keywords: *Flash Flood Susceptibility; Himalayan Mountain Region, Rainfall Intensity Analysis; Flood Inundation Mapping; Disaster Risk Assessment; Remote Sensing and GIS.*

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Bacteriocin for Sustainable Food Preservation: Enhancing Shelf Life, Quality, and Nutritional Integrity

Payel Sur^{1*}, Harekrishna Jana¹ and Mrinal Kanti Paira²

¹*Department of Microbiology, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Paschim Medinipur-721102, W.B., India.*

²*Department of Chemistry, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Paschim Medinipur-721102, W.B., India.*

**Email: payelsur96@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

To advance sustainable solutions for global food security and environmental impact, this study assessed the efficacy of a bacteriocin from *Pediococcus pentosaceus* HPM1 as a biocontrol agent against microbial spoilage in vegetables, fruits, meat, and fish, benchmarked against untreated controls under ambient and frozen storage. The results unequivocally demonstrate that treatment with the HPM1 bacteriocin consistently and significantly outperformed untreated conditions across all tested food types and storage environments. Under ambient storage, shelf life was substantially extended; for instance, tomatoes lasted 15 days compared to 7 in controls, and meat shelf life improved from 0.45 to 1.25 days. Similar positive impacts were seen in frozen storage, with apple shelf life increasing from 20 to 28 days. The bacteriocin's protective effects extended beyond mere shelf life, significantly preserving key quality parameters. Untreated samples exhibited considerable weight loss and divergent pH changes, whereas treated samples maintained a stable weight and minimal pH fluctuations. Furthermore, the integrity of nutritional composition was strongly linked to treatment: spoiled untreated foods showed statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) declines in carbohydrates, protein, and fat compared to fresh equivalents. In stark contrast, the HPM1 bacteriocin supernatant effectively prevented this degradation, maintaining nutrient levels in treated foods statistically similar to their fresh state. In conclusion, this investigation provides compelling evidence that *P. pentosaceus* HPM1 bacteriocin is a highly effective natural preservative, superior to no treatment in extending storage life and preserving the weight, pH stability, and nutritional quality of diverse foods, thereby offering a viable strategy for reducing food waste and supporting environmental sustainability.

Keywords: *Bacteriocin; Food Preservation; Shelf-Life Extension.*

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Impact of *Ganoderma lucidum* supplementation on human hematological and biochemical parameters: an approach of potential nutraceutical

Purna Nandi, Mrinal Kanti Paira, and Dilip Kumar Nandi*

Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's college (Autonomous), Midnapore-721102, India

**Email: dilipnandi2004@yahoo.co.in*

ABSTRACT

Ganoderma lucidum is commonly known as a traditional medicinal mushroom. It contains a huge amount of polysaccharides with molecular weights ranging from thousands to millions. The use of natural products is considered beneficial not only for human well being but also for the environment. The objectives present study is to observe the protective effect of *Ganoderma lucidum* by maintaining haematological and biochemical parameters. To compare between pre-intervention and post-intervention groups of *Ganoderma lucidum* (500mg/day and 1000mg/day) supplementation for 30 days and different parameters measured by using a hematoanalyzer, semi-auto analyzer. All the parameters are statistically analyzed by paired student t-tests. The Result fund that At the 15th day observation weight and glucose level was significantly decrease($p < 0.05$) after treatment also many enzymatic modulation observed. RBC, Hb and lymphocyte significantly increase($p < 0.05$) in post treatment group. However, the findings from this study suggested that *Ganoderma lucidum* may have the positive effect on liver and kidney by enzyme production regulation. This research work aims to report the effect of *Ganoderma lucidum* on human physiological parameters.

Keywords: *Ganoderma lucidum; Haematological parameters; Biochemical Markers.*

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**Embryonic Development, Larval Ontogeny, and Rearing of the Rainbow Shark
(*Epalzeorhynchus frenatum*)**

Sajal Maity¹, Gouranga Biswas^{1*}, Parimal Sardar¹, Paramita Banerjee Sawant², Udipta Roy³, Debajit Sarma², Tapas Kumar Ghoshal¹

¹ICAR-Central Institute of Fisheries Education, Kolkata Centre, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

²ICAR-Central Institute of Fisheries Education, Kolkata Centre, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

³ICAR-Central Institute of Fisheries Education, Motipur Centre, Motipur, Bihar, India

*Email: gouranga@cife.edu.in

ABSTRACT

The Rainbow shark (*Epalzeorhynchus frenatum*), native to Southeast Asia is a striking ornamental fish with greenish-brown body and vibrant red fins. Although this species can be induced bred, inconsistent success in captive breeding limits a steady supply resulted from the lack of information on embryonic development and larval ontogenesis. This information would standardize the seed production protocol by addressing the needs of each stage. In the present study, mature males (11.31±0.46 g) and females (16.98±1.3 g) at 2:1 ratio were induced to spawn by intramuscular injection of combined salmon gonadotropin-releasing hormone analogue and domperidone at 0.5 mL/kg body weight to females and 0.3 mL/kg to males. Spawning occurred between 6.5 and 7.5 h post injection. Spawning ova diameter was 1.08±0.04 mm and fertilized water-hardened eggs measured 3.67±0.15 mm. The developmental stages of live embryos documented using a Leica DFC 450 C light microscope indicated that the morula, blastula, gastrula, neurula, and organogenesis stages were completed at about 1.15 h, 2.10 h, 5.35 h, 6 h, and 9.5 h post-fertilization (hpf), respectively. Twitching movement in the developed embryos started at 9.30 hpf and hatching began at 13 hpf, with a hatching rate of 59.45 ± 3.80%. The newly hatched larvae measured 3.24±0.08 mm. The first feeding of larvae started at 72 hours of post hatching (hph). During larval rearing, the highest survival rate was observed in the group fed four times daily at a stocking density of 25 larvae/ litre of water, while the greatest weight gain was recorded in the group fed six times daily at the same stocking density. At the end of 30 days post hatching, the larvae grew up to 53.85±4.05 mm. This comprehensive information provides a valuable contribution to improving captive breeding and early-stage survival of the rainbow shark, supporting its sustainable seed production and trade.

Keywords: Rainbow shark; Embryonic development; Organogenesis; Larval rearing

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Sustainable Agriculture by Indigenous People: A Case Study of Birbhum District, West Bengal, India

Sajal Ghosh*

Department of Geography, Hiralal Bhakat College, Nalhati, West Bengal, India,

**Email:sajalghoshsuri@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

The Birbhum district is located in the latitude range of 23°32'30" to 24°35'00" N and the longitude range of 87°5'25" E to 88°1'40" E. The study area is characterized by lateritic features and riverine features with its diverse tribal and rural population offers rich examples of indigenous agriculture practices which is closely with the principles of sustainability. Major aims of this study is evaluate the contribution of these practices to sustainable farming such as soil fertility, crop diversity and climate resilience. This research apply a qualitative ethnographic method, gathering data from interviews, observation, oral traditions, and conversations, supplemented by secondary data. Purposive sampling was also apply for sampling collection., SWOT(Now SWOC) of MCDM analysis for sustainable agricultural practices through indigenous people. Major Santal tribe villages or indigenous villages of this study area includes Sayer para (23° 38' 50.18", 87° 34' 36.27"), Lakshmipur (23° 36' 55.78", 87° 35' 52.80"), Murgabuni (23° 37' 52.75", 87° 34' 33.88"), Dhalla (23° 38' 11.90", 87° 35' 06.34"), Daronda (23° 37' 30.45", 87° 36' 33.45"), Acchaipara (23° 39' 51.65", 87° 34' 45.82"). Major findings of this research that the indigenous practices of agriculture in Birbhum such as intercropping, used indigenous seed, using organic fertilizer, organic soil enrichment and water conservation techniques make a significant contribution to sustainable agriculture practices, soil health and resilience to erratic weather patterns.

Keywords: *Birbhum district; SWOC method; Climate resilience; Sustainable agriculture practices.*

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Evaluation of paraquat dichloride concentrations in environment with an emphasis on the biochemical implications on *Anabas testudineus* (bloch,1792) of both acute and chronic exposure.

Ganga Mandal*, Joydev Maity and Basudev Mandal

Department of Fishery Sciences, Vidyasagar University, Midnapore-721102, West Bengal, India.

Narajole Raj College, Narajole - 721211, West Bengal, India.

**Email: gangamandal8972@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Paraquat, a widely used non-selective herbicide, poses significant ecological hazards owing to its persistence and bioaccumulation potential. The present study investigates evaluation of paraquat dichloride (PD) concentrations in environment with an emphasis on the biochemical implications of both acute and chronic exposure. Samples of water and sediment were collected from khejuri, Purba Medinipur and analyzed by using HPLC. Fifty fish were divided into five groups based on four different concentrations of LC50 (25%, 50%, 75%, 100%) for 96 hours and 28 days of exposure, along with a control group for biochemical analysis, biochemical indicators such as blood glucose, serum protein, and enzyme activities (ALT, AST, and ALP). PD uses in field 6.5ml/L and occurrence on environment (soil ± 5.26 mg/kg and water ± 71.14 mg/l), result of HPLC reveals significant herbicide residues across all two matrices, confirming environmental persistence and bioaccumulation. Biochemical analysis showed elevated blood glucose (52.32 ± 6.42 to 88.32 ± 6.91) and cholesterol levels at first increases as time and conc. of PD increases (221.12 ± 5.80 to 198.98 ± 4.66) then after 14 days the cholesterol levels decreases, suggesting stress, along with alterations in protein levels that decreases (6.35 ± 1.38 to 1.06 ± 1.05). Elevated aminotransferase, alanine aminotransferase and alkaline phosphatase indicated hepatic and renal impairment. Changes were greater and more persistent after chronic exposure than in the acute toxicity test. These findings underline the ecological risk posed by PD contamination and support the use of environmental monitoring and risk assessment.

Keywords: *Paraquat dichloride, Anabas testudineus, Bioaccumulation, West Bengal, Alkaline phosphatase.*

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Arctic Soil Microbial diversity studies for Biotechnological potential

Md Raihan Uddin* and Sukhendu Mandal

Department of Physiology, Raja Narendra Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous)

²*Department of Microbiology, Calcutta University*

*Email: mdrahn@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Polar microbiology remains as the most fascinating area of research which mainly focuses on exploration of psychrophilic organisms for having their cold-active enzymes of biotechnological potential. The optimal growth parameters of most of the isolates are ranges between 15-22°C temperature, 2-5 days of incubation, 6-10 pH, and 3-7% (w/v) NaCl in LB media. We performed molecular systematic, carbon and nitrogen utilization pattern along with temperature, P^H and NaCl tolerance range of these isolates were investigated. Among these isolates, investigation shows that 65% isolates are positive to lipase production, 18% amylase, 7% xylanase and 7% isolates have responded for phosphates activity. Among those isolate one potent lipase producing strain RSAP22 detailed morphological, biochemical, chemotaxonomy and molecular characteristics were investigated to characterize. Analyses of the 16S rDNA sequence of strain RSAP22 shows the closest match with *Marinobacter aromaticivorans* (98.36%) and *Marinobacter maritimus* (97.81%). Phylogenetic analysis reveals that RSAP22 has been grouped into *Marinobacter aromaticivorans* in tree making algorithm NJ, ML & MP. Elsewhere physiochemical data, fatty acid profile compare to closest ancestor based on 16S gene similar shows it is far different and probably a novel strain. A variety of cold tolerant enzymes counting lipases, proteases, amylases, cellulases have big requirement in the global market for their useful purpose in the detergent, food and biofuel and biotechnological industries.

Keywords: *Polar Microbiolgy; Soil, Characterization; Novel bacteria; Enzyme, Biotechnology industries*

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**Studies of helminth parasite infections in *Anabas testudineus* (Bloch,1792) at Tamluk,
Purba Medinipur, West Bengal, India**

Antara Mahapatra* and Biplab Mandal

Department of Zoology, Tamralipta Mahavidyalaya, Tamluk 721636, Purba Medinipur, West Bengal.

Department of Zoology, Vidyasagar University, Midnapore 721102, West Bengal.

**Email: amahapatra9800@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

A total of 180 *Anabas testudineus* were examined to assess the occurrence of helminth parasites and their relationship with host size and sex. Of these, 112 individuals (62.22%) were found infected with representatives of Acanthocephala, Nematoda and Trematoda. The study aimed to determine whether infection varied with length, weight and sex of the host. For analytical convenience, fishes were grouped into three size classes: smaller, medium and larger length categories, which corresponded proportionately with lower, intermediate and higher body weights. Prevalence was calculated separately for each class. The smaller length group exhibited comparatively low prevalence, indicating limited exposure or reduced susceptibility. The moderate length group showed an intermediate level of infection increasing contact with infective stages as feeding intensity and habitat range expanded. In contrast, fishes belonging to the larger length and weight class revealed the highest prevalence. This trend reflects cumulative exposure over time, broader dietary spectrum and prolonged environmental interaction, all of which enhance the probability of parasite acquisition. The gradual rise in prevalence from smaller to larger fishes supports a size-dependent pattern of infection. A chi-square (χ^2) test was performed to evaluate the significance of sex-wise variation in infection. The calculated χ^2 value exceeded the critical value ($p < 0.05$), indicating a statistically significant difference between sexes. Higher infection in females may be associated with physiological stress during gonadal development, hormonal influences, or differential feeding behaviour. This study demonstrates that helminth prevalence increases with host length and weight, and that host sex plays a significant role in parasitic infection dynamics.

Keywords: *Anabas testudineus; Helminth; Parasite burden; Size-dependent infection; Prevalence.*

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Impact of anthropogenic stressors on vulnerability of microinvertebrate communities in hyporheic sediment at Damodar riverbed, India.

Baisakhi Chakraborty* and Pravat Kumar Shit

Jagannath Kishore College, Purulia, West Bengal, India.

Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Medinipur, West Bengal, India.

*Email: bchakraborty201595@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Hyporheic zone plays vital role on inhabitation of invertebrate communities that maintains total metabolism of river ecosystem. In hyporheic zone of riverbed, surface and subsurface water interact with each other with various physio-chemical components, nutrients and heavy metals through upwelling and downwelling process. In this study responses of microinvertebrate species with sediment physio-chemical, heavy metal properties in a selected area of Damodar riverbed has been analyzed. Total ten (10) hyporheic sediment samples were collected from nine different longitudinal cross sections from 10-20 cm depth of riverbed. Total six (06) communities were identified from those samples among Copepoda are dominant species (21.77%) and Ostracoda have lowest population (9.36%). Sample -10 have contained maximum population (19.49%) and sample-8 contained least population (3.29%). Ostracoda and Rotifera are absent in sample 5, 8 and 9. Principal component analysis have identified properties like pH, sulphet, calcium, magnesium, zinc, fluoride, copper etc have negative correlation with BOD, EC, TSS, microinvertebrates and microbial communities. This relationship indicated extreme discharge of organic and inorganic substances that rises microbial activity and oxygen demand of metabolic process in waterbody. Negative influence of physio-chemical parameters decreased invertebrate population in hyporheic zone and therefore suitable remediation techniques are highly necessary for control riverbed pollution to sustain aquatic ecosystem and biodiversity.

Keywords: Hyporheic zone; Microinvertebrate; Principal Component Analysis; Correlation; Riverbed pollution; Remediation

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Indo-Pacific Tarpon (*Megalops cyprinoides*)

Pritish Bera*, Joydev Maity and Basudev Mandal

Department of Fishery Sciences, Vidyasagar University, Midnapore-721102, West Bengal, India.

Narajole Raj College, Narajole, Paschim Midnapore - 721211, West Bengal, India.

**Email: pritishbera98@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Megalops cyprinoides, commonly known as the Indo-Pacific tarpon, is a euryhaline teleost widely distributed in coastal and estuarine waters of the Indo-West Pacific region. The Atlantic tarpon's air-breathing organ (ABO) consists of four parallel ridges of alveolar-like respiratory tissue that run the length of the physostomous gas bladder. Each ridge's broad and complicated surface is made up of a cartilage matrix that is entirely infiltrated with a thin respiratory epithelium. Histological observations reveal a rich network of blood capillaries and a thin epithelial lining, facilitating efficient gaseous exchange. These findings indicate that older tarpon that live in better oxygenated maritime coastal areas retain the air-breathing capacity that immature fish require for survival in their hypoxic nursery habitat. Adult tarpon's retention of air breathing may be linked to their occasional occurrence in hypoxic environments and high rates of aerobic metabolism. This fish has cycloid scales, but some new variations can be observed within these scales. Seven finger lines are present on both the lateral line scales and the ventral scales, with the finger lines being distinct on the lateral line scales and progressively less clear on the ventral scales. The first dorsal fin is made of hard rays, while the last dorsal fin is soft, with the rays of the last dorsal fin being elongated. Therefore, the unique structure of the scales and dorsal fin distinguishes this species externally from other fish species. The accessory respiratory mechanism is particularly crucial during the juvenile stages, when individuals commonly inhabit shallow coastal and brackish waters where dissolved oxygen levels frequently fluctuate. The presence of specialized air-breathing organ enables *Megalops cyprinoides* to survive in oxygen-depleted (hypoxic) environments such as estuaries, mangrove swamps, and coastal lagoons. These anatomical features highlight its ecological resilience and biological importance in tropical coastal fisheries.

Keywords: *Megalops cyprinoides; Indo-Pacific tarpon; air-breathing organ; swim bladder; cycloid scales; fin rays; functional morphology; estuarine adaptation.*

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**Occupational Exposure to Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) and Health Outcomes among
Brick Kiln Workers in West Bengal, India.**

Mantu Paira* and Bela Das

*Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College, Research Centre in Natural and Applied Sciences,
Midnapore-721102, West Bengal, India
Email: mantupaira_geo@rnlkwc.ac.in

ABSTRACT

Workers often inhale the air pollution from brick kilns, particularly the PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. The long-term effects of such pollutants can lead to adverse health outcomes, particularly respiratory irritation and different health related problems. This paper examines how exposure to air pollution affects the health of brick kiln workers in West Bengal, India. A cross-sectional survey was carried out on 582 workers in 13 brick kilns in Howrah and Murshidabad districts of West Bengal. Air pollution at major working points was measured by portable Dyllos DC air quality monitoring equipment that was used to measure the concentrations of PM within the working hours of the day. Also, a structured questionnaire on the health condition of workers was done. The questionnaire contained the symptoms that are usually related to being exposed to air pollution, including cough, difficulty breathing or wheezing, irritation of the nose, sore throat, eye irritation, itchiness, rash, headache, dizziness, and nausea. The frequency of each of the reported symptoms was reported on an ordinal scale between never and often. The prevalence of health symptoms in workers was estimated through descriptive statistics. Factor analysis was used to identify latent dimensions of pollution-related health outcomes, and structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to assess the relationship between exposure to PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ and health outcomes. The results show that the respiratory symptoms and the irritation symptoms are prevalent in the brick kiln workers, and a significant percentage of them experienced frequent cough, throat irritation, eye irritation, and skin issues. According to the SEM results, there is a substantive positive correlation between the increase in the levels of particulate matter and the risk of respiratory and general health symptoms. The health risks associated with pollution among the workers in the brick kiln industries in West Bengal need to be mitigated by enhancing the dust control methods and workplace safety measures as well as regular health monitoring programs.

Keywords: *Air pollution; PM_{2.5}; Respiratory problem; SEM; Health effect.*

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Climate Change: Emerging Challenges for Urban Infrastructure in India

Pragna Paramita Roy
Department of Geography
Dr. Shyama Prasad Mukherjee University
P.O. - Ranchi University Morabadi Ranchi- 834008.
paramitapragna2018@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Over the past few decades, Indian cities have increasingly faced severe impacts from climate change. Urban areas across the country are exposed to various climate-related challenges almost every year. Rising global temperatures, particularly during the summer months, have intensified the phenomenon of urban heat islands in cities such as Delhi, Ganganagar, Jaisalmer, Churu, Hisar, and Rohtak, causing significant discomfort and health risks for residents. In addition, coastal cities frequently experience flooding and other extreme weather events as a result of the harsh effects of climate change, making them particularly vulnerable. Major coastal metropolitan areas such as Mumbai, Chennai, and Kolkata are witnessing recurring damage to infrastructure due to these climate-related disasters. Infrastructure failures, acute summer water shortages, declining public health conditions, and environmental degradation are increasingly affecting urban life in India. Like cities in both developing and developed countries worldwide, Indian cities must adopt urgent and sustainable measures to address the growing threat of climate change. Strengthening public awareness, promoting afforestation, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, minimizing dependence on fossil fuels, and implementing effective government policies and urban planning initiatives can significantly help mitigate the adverse impacts of climate change.

Keywords: *Climate Change; Urban Infrastructure; Urban Heat Island; Coastal Vulnerability; Urban Flooding; Sustainable Urban Planning; Climate Adaptation.*

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**Present Status of Fish Faunal Diversity and Social Stress Affecting Aquatic Biodiversity of the
Keleghai River, West Bengal, India**

Prabir Khalua* and Mrinmay Ghorai

*Centre for Fisheries Research, Department of Zoology
Panskura Banamali College (Autonomous)
Panskura R.S., Purba Medinipur – 721152, West Bengal, India
Email: prabirkhalua233@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Fish faunal diversity has been declining in several rivers of West Bengal in recent decades, resulting in many species becoming endangered or vulnerable. The Keleghai River in the Midnapore district was once rich in fish diversity; however, the aquatic ecosystem is currently under severe stress due to various anthropogenic pressures. The present study conducts an empirical investigation of fish faunal diversity and the effects of social stress in the Midnapore district of West Bengal. A total of 69 fish species belonging to 11 orders, 29 families, and 36 genera have been recorded in this region. However, qualitative investigation reveals that several social stress factors-such as the expansion of brick kilns along riverbanks, the proliferation of prawn fisheries, and extensive soil extraction from riverbanks using earth-moving machinery-have significantly disrupted the natural water flow and caused shrinkage of the river basin. These human interventions directly affect water quality and lead to a decline in fish faunal diversity in the Keleghai River. This study highlights that fish diversity is strongly influenced by various social and anthropogenic pressures. The findings emphasize the urgent need for long-term monitoring programs and habitat restoration initiatives to mitigate the impact of these stresses on aquatic biodiversity in the middle and downstream regions of the Keleghai River. To conserve these valuable biological resources, a holistic approach integrating sustainable development and conservation measures is essential.

Keywords: *Fish Faunal Diversity; Keleghai River; Aquatic Biodiversity; Anthropogenic Stress; River Ecosystem; Habitat Degradation; Sustainable Conservation.*

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**Comparative Trends of Bheri Farming and Agricultural Land in 2010 and 2025: A
Study of Bhagwanpur-I Block, Purba Medinipur, West Bengal**

Nityananda Shit*
Centre for Environmental Studies, Vidyasagar University, Midnapore-721102
*Email: info.nityananda@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The present study aims to examine the decline of agricultural land, the expansion of *bheri* farming, and the factors responsible for the conversion of agricultural land into aquaculture in Bhagwanpur-I Block of Purba Medinipur district, West Bengal. In this region, several freshwater fish species such as Rohu (*Labeo rohita*), Catla (*Catla catla*), and Mrigal (*Cirrhinus mrigala*) are cultivated along with brackish water shrimp species, including *Penaeus monodon* and *Penaeus vannamei*. Many farmers lease their agricultural lands to fishery owners for a fixed period in expectation of higher economic returns compared to traditional paddy cultivation. To analyse this land-use transformation, Remote Sensing and Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques were applied to identify the decline of agricultural land and the expansion of *bheri* farming over a fifteen-year period from 2010 to 2025. Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) classification was performed using satellite imagery and ArcGIS 10.8 software. The results derived from satellite image analysis indicate a significant change in the land-use pattern during the study period. The total cropland area was 129.82 sq. km in 2010, which decreased to 104.00 sq. km in 2025. In contrast, the aquaculture area increased from 0.96 sq. km in 2010 to 22.74 sq. km in 2025. Overall, the cropland area declined by approximately 14.45%, while the aquaculture area increased by about 12.50% during the study period.

Keywords: *Bheri Farming; Agricultural Land; Land Use Land Cover (LULC); Aquaculture Expansion; Remote Sensing and GIS; Land Conversion.*

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**Prevalence of Stunting and Underweight among Santal Adolescent Boys (10–17 Years)
of Jhargram District, West Bengal: A Cross-Sectional Study**

Swarup Pratihar and Kaushik Bose
Department of Anthropology, Vidyasagar University
Email: swaruppratiharanthro2015@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Under nutrition among adolescents remains a major public health concern in India, particularly among socio-economically marginalized tribal communities. Stunting and underweight are important indicators of chronic and acute nutritional deficiencies that can adversely affect physical growth, cognitive development, and overall health during adolescence. In India, several studies indicate that a substantial proportion of adolescents suffer from under nutrition. The present study aims to examine the effect of socio-demographic variables on the nutritional status of Santal adolescent boys aged 10-17 years in the Jhargram district of West Bengal. A community-based cross-sectional study design was employed. Anthropometric measurements, including height and weight, were collected following standard procedures. Nutritional status was assessed using the IAP (Indian Academy of Paediatrics) growth reference standards. Stunting was defined as height-for-age Z-score (HAZ) <-2 SD, while underweight was determined using weight-for-age criteria. The results revealed that the overall prevalence of stunting was 24.0% and underweight was 13.6% among the studied population. According to the WHO (1995) classification, the prevalence of stunting and underweight indicates a moderate public health concern. Socio-demographic factors such as monthly family income, age group, father's occupation, and birth order were found to be significant predictors of stunting. Similarly, age, mother's occupation, family income, and birth order were significant determinants of underweight. Higher income levels and maternal occupation as housewife or day labourer showed a positive association with improved nutritional outcomes. However, other factors such as sanitation, place of residence, and family composition did not show statistically significant effects. The findings suggest that the nutritional status of the studied population remains unsatisfactory and requires targeted public health interventions.

Keywords: Stunting; Underweight; Adolescent Boys; Santal Tribe; Nutritional Status; Socio-demographic Factors; Jhargram District.

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**Documentation and Analysis of Avian Diversity and Community Structure in the
Sundarban Tiger Reserve, West Bengal**

Somanka Sanyal*, Sanchari Pal, Debojyoti Pradhan, Aniket Bhowmick and Santipriya Maity

*Ecology and Ecotoxicology Laboratory, Department of Biological Sciences, Midnapore City College,
Kuturiya, Bhadutala, Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal, India.*

*Email: somanka85@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Birds are among the most visible and ecologically significant organisms found across a wide range of ecosystems. They perform several essential ecological functions, including pollination, seed dispersal and the regulation of pest populations. The composition of bird communities can strongly influence the diversity of other organisms and birds are widely recognized as reliable bioindicators of environmental conditions, particularly water chemistry and ecosystem health. Information on bird species composition is therefore crucial for understanding ecosystem services and for designing effective conservation strategies within specific geographic regions. The present study examines the diversity of bird species at three locations- Sudhanyakhali Watch Tower, Sajnekhali Wildlife Sanctuary and Pakhiralay within the Sundarban Tiger Reserve in the South 24 Parganas district of West Bengal, India. During the survey, a total of 32 bird species were documented, representing 29 genera, 23 families, and 8 different orders. The order Passeriformes was the most dominant, accounting for 47% of the recorded species with 15 species followed by other avian orders. Among the identified species, 30 were resident birds while 2 were migratory. All recorded species are legally protected under the Wildlife (Protection) Amendment Act, 2022. The bird species were also categorized according to their feeding habits. Carnivorous species formed the largest group comprising 35% of the total, followed by omnivorous species at 25%. The findings from this study provide valuable baseline data on bird diversity and community structure in the study area. Such documentation is important for evaluating avifaunal diversity and will contribute to the development and implementation of future conservation and management strategies.

Keywords: *Avifaunal diversity; Omnivore; Passeriformes; Pollination; Conservation*

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**Human–Environment Interactions and Land Use Transformation in the Mangrove
Ecosystem: A Spatial–Socioeconomic Analysis of North 24 Parganas**

Rejaul Islam Sana*
Department of Geography
Hiralal Bhakat College
Nalhati, Birbhum, West Bengal
**Email: rejaulgeo@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Land use dynamics refers to the temporal and spatial changes in the way land is utilized by humans due to socio-economic activities and environmental processes. As these dynamic behaviour constitute a long-term human footprint on the earth's surface, a thorough understanding of land use dynamics is required for successful strategic planning and sustainable natural resource management. This research explores the Sundarban region's changing land use patterns, tracking their evolution from early British land reclamation projects in the North 24 Parganas to present environmental alterations. Specifically, the study looks at the compounding effects of rapid population growth and the subsequent extension of settlement areas. Six parameters have been taken to run AHP viz. Coastal Slope, Furthermore, it examines critical contemporary shifts in the region's economic landscape, particularly the shift from traditional agricultural practices—such as mono-cropping and scattered multi-cropping—to the steady conversion of farmlands into seaward-extending fisheries, as well as the proliferation of riverside brick kilns. This study emphasises the shifting human-environment interactions and their implications for the Sundarban ecosystem by focusing on these complex spatial changes.

Keywords: *Land Use Dynamics; Sundarban Region; Natural Resource Management; Land Reclamation; Agricultural Conversion; Human-Environment Interaction*

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Sponsored by Department of Science and Technology & Biotechnology (DSTBT),
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**Between Reward and Retribution: Ancient Indian Ethical Frameworks for
Environmental Sustainability**

Srimanta Bhadra*

*Dept. of Sanskrit, Raja Narendralal Khan Women's College (Autonomous), Midnapore-721102,
West Bengal, India.*

*Email: srimantabhadra@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

All across the world, the people are facing a wealth of new and challenging environmental problems every day. Environmental pollution ranges right from air pollution, water pollution and land pollution, thermal pollution, visual pollution, sea pollution to sound pollution to ultimately mental, intellectual, psychic and cultural pollution. As we, the modern people speak of protecting the environment, we think about the modern technology, i.e. using of solar energy, wind energy etc. and think of reducing the use of fossils, of reducing greenhouse gas emissions, of deforestation, of planting more plants, of controlling the source of air pollution, water pollution and global warming and so on and so forth. But besides modern technology, we can also learn much from our ancient texts, i.e. Veda, Smṛti, Purāṇa, Arthaśāstra, Epics etc. In the early age the Rishis and scholars are used to talk about two types of result of any activity – material (Aihika) and spiritual (Paralaukika), in modern term buy one get one free like that. The result may be rewarded or punishment. In my paper I will focus on the consciousness of the ancestors on environmental issues, briefly what the steps were taken for Environmental Sustainability and what was the punishment for damaging the environment of the surroundings. In conclusion, this study highlights how immortal ideas from ancient texts can inform modern strategies for safeguarding the environment.

Keywords: *Environmental Pollution; Environmental Sustainability; Ancient Indian Texts; Traditional Ecological Knowledge; Environmental Ethics.*

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Integrated Assessment of Groundwater Level and Storage Changes Using Innovative Trend Analysis (ITA), GRACE Data, and Google Earth Engine for Sustainable Environmental Management

Arijit Ghosh*

Department of Geography,

Noida International University, Greater Noida, India

**Email: arijitwbgeo@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Globally, groundwater is a crucial freshwater source and the third-largest water resource. Groundwater issues in the Manbhum-Singhbhum Plateau have intensified in recent decades due to overextraction and poor irrigation practices, resulting in ecosystem degradation and contamination. The objective of this study is to examine changes in groundwater levels over the past two decades and assess variations in groundwater storage in an Indian hard-rock terrain. Observed groundwater level data were analysed using the Innovative Trend Analysis (ITA) method, and satellite-based data from the Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE) were utilized to estimate Terrestrial Water Storage (TWS). Groundwater Storage (GWS) was calculated as TWS minus soil moisture obtained from the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform. The findings indicate that about 40% of monitoring sites experienced a notable decrease in groundwater levels during the pre-monsoon season, rising to 67.5% in the post-monsoon season. The highest groundwater storage (9.48 cm) was observed in July 2004, and the lowest (-30.21 cm) in March 2016. Thus, the results display considerable reductions in groundwater levels and storage, primarily caused by geological factors and over-extraction for irrigation and drinking. The results emphasize the persistent need for effective management of groundwater resources in the Manbhum-Singhbhum Plateau.

Keywords: *Groundwater level change; Groundwater storage; Innovative Trend Analysis (ITA); GRACE satellite data; Google Earth Engine (GEE); Terrestrial Water Storage (TWS)*

Trees are the earth's endless effort to speak to the listening heaven.

Rabindranath Tagore